

PRE-PUBLICATION VERSION

"To sing on Shabbat evening and day, each person at their table":

On the Medieval Development of the Custom to Sing Shabbat Zemirot

Dedicated to the memory of my mother, Monica Rasch-Kohn z"l (1957-2015).

Introduction:¹

Most scholarly interest in medieval Jewish song focuses on the liturgy.² But what of the world of song outside the synagogue? Instances of both devotional and celebratory communal singing were sprinkled throughout the Jewish calendar. The 11th-century sage Yosef Tov-Elem observed already that his coreligionists bid farewell to the Shabbat on Saturday evening as medieval people would a king departing from their village, “with joyousness and songs.”³

Abraham b. Nathan reports that the Jews of France, in contrast to those in Spain who sang these post-Shabbat songs in the synagogue, were accustomed to sing them in their homes.⁴ Numerous

¹ This project has come together thanks to the guidance and assistance of many scholars over the years. I would like to thank Professors Elisheva Baumgarten, Elisheva Carlebach and Benjamin Gampel who supervised my research at different stages. Special thanks are owed to Dr. Justine Isserles, who generously offered her paleographic expertise in support of my work. Dr. Gabriel Wasserman similarly played a major role in supporting and guiding my thinking from the outset of my work. Thanks to Professor Marjorie Lehman, Dr. Andreas Lehnertz, Dr. Eyal Levenson, and Hannah Teddy Shachter for their comments and feedback. This project has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement no. 681507), *Beyond the Elite: Jewish Daily Life in Medieval Europe*, directed by Elisheva Baumgarten.

² For recent studies focused on the synagogue, see Eliyahu Schleifer, “Maharil (Mainz ca. 1365 - Worms 1427): The Mythical Father of Ashkenazic Synagogue Chant” in *Jüdische Kultur in den SchUM-Städten*, ed. K. E. Grözingen (Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2014), 247-260; Sarit Shalev-Eyni, “The Aural-Visual Experience in the Ashkenazic Ritual Domain of the Middle Ages” in *Resounding Images: Medieval Intersections of Art, Music, and Sound*, eds. S. Boynton and D. J. Reilly (Turnhout: Brepols, 2015), 189-204.

³ *Mahzor Vitry*, ed. Arie Goldschmidt (Jerusalem: Mekhon Otsar Ha-poskim, 2004), Vol. 2, 306.

⁴ Abraham b. Nathan of Lunel, *Sefer Ha-manhig*, ed. S. Rafael (Jerusalem: Mossad Ha-rav Kook, 1975), Vol. 1, 198.

medieval manuscripts include songs for this weekly occasion that praise the Shabbat and, later in the Middle Ages, call upon the Prophet Elijah for support in the new week.⁵

A less common, yet equally important, opportunity for communal singing was weddings. Research into medieval Jewish weddings and their celebrations has highlighted the festive singing that accompanied them.⁶ Isaac b. Moses of Vienna (1200-1270) points to communal singing as part of the extended wedding celebrations when he remarks that in his region “on Friday evening of Shabbat when there are weddings, they sing songs around the table.”⁷ Other sources describe communities coming together to sing and dance in celebration of the new couple.⁸ Clearly, singing outside of the synagogue was a prominent element of medieval Jewish life.

This essay will explore Jewish singing by outlining the development of another instance of communal or, more specifically, familial singing that is attested to with increasing frequency among Jews of Europe over the course of the Middle Ages: the singing of Shabbat table-songs.⁹ Generally, these table-songs are called Shabbat *Zemirot*, *Zemer* in the singular referring to a para-liturgical poem recited outside of the formal synagogue service.¹⁰ The custom to sing around the table on Shabbat is mentioned frequently in overviews of medieval Jewish life and

⁵ A collection of these songs can be found in *Mahzor Vitry*, ed. Goldschmidt, Vol. 2, 307-321. The author is grateful to Dr. Chana Shacham-Rashby for sharing her work on the reception of the Prophet Elijah in Ashkenaz.

⁶ Kirsten A. Fudeman, *Vernacular Voices: Language and Identity in Medieval French Jewish Communities* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2010); Idem., “‘They Have Ears, but Do Not Hear’: Gendered Access to Hebrew and the Medieval Hebrew-French Wedding Song,” *JQR* 96.4 (2006): 542-67; Esther Cohen and Elliot Horowitz, “In Search of the Sacred: Jews, Christians, and Rituals of Marriage in the Later Middle Ages,” *The Journal of Medieval and Renaissance Studies* 20.2 (1990): 225-49.

⁷ Isaac b. Moses of Vienna, *Sefer Or Zaru’a*, ed. Y. Farbstein (Jerusalem: Mekhon Yerushalayim, 2001), Vol. 2, 43.

⁸ Adi Namia-Cohen, “‘Minhag bi-a’shkenaz li-ekhol’: A’khila ve-a’rikhat seudot bi-krav yehudei a’shkenaz (1100-1300),” MA Thesis (Hebrew University, 2020), 60-73.

⁹ On defining song in the Middle Ages, John Haines, *Medieval Song in Romance Languages* (Cambridge: University of Cambridge Press, 2016), 10-13. For a printed edition of the Shabbat *Zemirot* with some commentary based on early prints and manuscripts, *Zemirot shel Shabbat*, ed. Naphtali Ben-Menachem (Jerusalem, 1949).

¹⁰ Avraham Fraenkel, “Ha-zemer al hatzalat Worms v-zman chiburo shel ‘Maoz Tzur’,” *Hamaayan* 208 (2014), 15; Ezra Fleisher, *Hebrew Liturgical Poetry in the Middle Ages* (Jerusalem: Magnes Press, 2007), 412 [in Hebrew].

music.¹¹ In-depth analyses, though, have almost exclusively considered the practice in its early modern and modern iterations.¹² Others have narrowly focused on individual songs¹³ or the customs of particular groups within the Jewish tradition.¹⁴ Aside from a brief discussion by Tova Beeri, the history of the ritual's formation in the Middle Ages has not received serious attention.¹⁵

Because proper musical notation was not provided for Shabbat Zemirot until at least the 18th century, any study of these songs must follow recent scholarly trends and focus on their socio-cultural as opposed to musical significance.¹⁶ This article will trace the development and spread of the practice to sing during Friday evening and Saturday afternoon meals through the age of print. Although Shabbat table-singing was likely common for centuries, our earliest extant written instructions to sing specific songs were composed in 13th-century northern France to

¹¹ Daniel Goldschmidt, "Zemirot" in *Encyclopedia Judaica*, 2nd ed., eds. F. Skolnik, and M. Berenbaum (Detroit: Macmillan Reference USA, 2007), Vol. 21, 507; Abraham Z. Idelsohn, *Jewish Music in Its Historical Development* (New York: Schocken Books, 1967), 361, 384-5; Idem., *Jewish Liturgy and its Development* (New York: Schocken Books, 1967), 151-7; Macy Nulman, *Concise Encyclopedia of Jewish Music* (New York: McGraw-Hill, 1975), 269-270; Israel Abrahams, *Jewish Life in the Middle Ages* (Philadelphia: Jewish Publication Society, 1993), 133-137; Alfred Sendrey, *The Music of the Jews in the Diaspora* (New York: T. Yoseloff, 1971), 177-182.

¹² Macy Nulman, "Mah Yafit—the Intriguing Fate of the Shabbat Table Hymn," *Journal of Jewish Music and Liturgy* 1.1 (1976): 27-38; Edwin Seroussi and Israel Adler, "Musical Notations of Zemîrôt (Sabbath Table Songs) in an Eighteenth-Century Manuscript at the Prague National Library," *Studies in Bibliography and Booklore* 20 (1998): 5-24; Avery Gosfield, "Gratias post mensam in diebus festiuis cum cantico העבריים: A New Look at an Early Sixteenth-Century Tzur Mishelo" in *Revealing the Secrets of the Jews*, eds. J. Adams and C. Heß (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2017), 275-296; Naomi Cohn Zentner, *Reshuffling the Ashkenazic Musical Heritage in Domestic Spheres: The Singing of Zemirot Shabbat among Religious Zionists in Israel*, Doctoral Dissertation (Hebrew University of Jerusalem, 2013) [in Hebrew].

¹³ Macy Nulman, "Mah Yafit," 27-38; Tova Beeri, "'Zur Mi-Shelo Achalnu' — A Sabbath Song" *Jerusalem Studies in Hebrew Literature* 11 (1978): 419-443 [in Hebrew].

¹⁴ Riikka Tuori, "Polish-Lithuanian Karaite Hebrew Zemirot: Imitation only? A Review on a marginal genre" in *Traveling Through Time: Essays in Honor of Kaj Öhrnberg*, eds. S. Akar, J. Hämeen-Anttila and I. Nokso-Koivisto (Helsinki, 2013), 359-372; Moshe Halamish, *Kabbalistic customs of Shabbat* (Jerusalem: Magnes Press, 2006), 342-353; Liebes, "Zemirot li-s'eudot shabbat she-yasad ha-ari ha-qodesh," *Molad* 23 (1972): 540-555.

¹⁵ Beeri, "'Zur Mi-Shelo Achalnu,'" 423.

¹⁶ This approach is best exemplified by studies of singing during Reformation. See, Daniel Trocme-Latter, *The Singing of the Strasbourg Protestants, 1523-1541* (New York: Routledge, 2016), 9-13; Rebecca Oettinger, "Thomas Murner, Michael Stifel, and Songs as Polemic in the Early Reformation," *Journal of Musicological Research* 22.1-2 (2003): 45-100. Unlike these works, the present article will engage only minimally with the lyrics of Shabbat Zemirot. On the themes of the songs themselves, see Meir Nizri, "Israel and the Sabbath as Bride and Groom in Various Sabbath Hymns" in *Jerusalem Studies in Jewish Folklore* 30, eds. H. Salamon, G. Hasan-Rokem and S. Sabar (Jerusalem: Magnes Press, 2016), 179-246 [in Hebrew].

help satisfy the ritual requirement to eat three meals over the course of Shabbat. Instructions to sing these same songs appear soon after in Ashkenaz and then in Italy without their original Halakhic framing.¹⁷ The numerous manuscripts containing Shabbat Zemirot reveal the rapid spread and development of the practice in these regions. Though preserved in writing, Shabbat Zemirot and their melodies were primarily transmitted orally by families singing in their homes. Such orality encouraged flexibility and diversity in how people sang Shabbat Zemirot throughout the Middle Ages. When Shabbat Zemirot were printed in the 16th century, however, a more rigid understanding of the practice and its repertoire of songs took shape. Those songs which were printed in the 16th century still constitute the majority of Shabbat Zemirot recited to this day. In the appendices, the reader will find complete lists of manuscripts containing Shabbat Zemirot from northern France/Ashkenaz and Italy as well as a catalogue of the most common songs found in those manuscripts.

The Origins of Shabbat Zemirot:

It is likely that by the Middle Ages, table-singing had long been a common Jewish practice. Various comments found in early medieval rabbinic literature suggest that Jews were singing around their tables even before the appearance of the detailed medieval evidence.¹⁸ For example, in the 11th-century *Chronicle of Aḥima'az*, we are told that the scholars of Jerusalem, sitting down to eat, initiated “lovely singing and pleasant hymn.”¹⁹ The earliest explicit discussion of Shabbat table-singing, though, comes from the end of the 12th century. In *Sefer Ḥasidim*, a collection of ritual-lore and pious practices attributed to Judah b. Samuel of

¹⁷ It should be noted that in the body of this article, Ashkenaz refers to the Jewish communities of German-speaking lands and does not, as it sometimes does, include the communities of northern France.

¹⁸ For rabbinic sources, Menachem Eichorn, *Sefer zemirat tsion* (Toronto, 2013), 22-28.

¹⁹ *History and Folklore in a Medieval Jewish Chronicle: The Family Chronicle of Aḥima'az ben Paltiel*, ed. & trans. R. Bonfil (Leiden: Brill, 2009), 248-249.

Regensburg, known as *Judah He-hasid* (the Pious) (d. 1217), singing during Shabbat meals is ascribed a Biblical source:

And God blessed the seventh day (Gen. 2:3), but it does not explain how? Rather, it is in those things which Job cursed the day of his birth. *Let a cloud dwell upon it* (Job 3:5), *Let it not rejoice among the days of the year* (Job 3:6) . . . Thereby they should sit on Shabbat in light and one should sit and sing praises as it says *A song to sing for the Shabbat day. It is good to offer thanks to God and to sing* (Psalms 92:1) and rejoice on the Shabbat in the precepts of God.²⁰

Because Job describes a cursed day as dark and absent of rejoicing, the exegete determines that the blessedness of the Shabbat is found in its light and singing. As the light likely refers to the Shabbat candles lit each week in the home, the singing can be assumed to be that which accompanied the domestic shabbat meals.²¹ Judah's student, Eleazar of Worms (1176-1238), similarly advocates for table-singing when he writes that "there should also be songs of praise to the Holy Blessed One and to the Shabbat around the table, for this is the meaning of the verse *they will joyously shout before you* (Isa. 55:12)."²² It is unsurprising that these figures would encourage singing at Shabbat meals since their other writings frequently mention the spiritual value of incorporating melodies into one's religious life and specifically into one's prayers.²³ Though these comments indicate that singing on Shabbat was a practice known at least to these sages, they do not shed light on what songs were being sung.

²⁰ *Sefer Ḥasidim*, ed. J. Wistinetzki (Berlin: H. Itzkowski, 1891), 166 (#622). For alternative versions of this teaching found in various manuscripts, see *Princeton University Sefer Ḥasidim Project* (PUSHP), https://etc.princeton.edu/sefer_Hasidim/manuscripts.php, JTS Boesky 45, #276, 522; Parma 3280 H, #622, 1296; Bologna Print 1538, #409, 1153; Cambridge Univ. Lib. Add 379, #412.

²¹ For discussion of the candles on Shabbat, see Ariella Lehmann, "'Mi sh-tarah bi-erev shabbat': Hakhanot le-shabbat etsel yehudei a'shkenaz bi'yemei ha-beinei'im," MA Thesis (Hebrew University, 2018), 13-49.

²² Eleazar b. Judah, *Perushei siddur ha-tefilah la-rokeah*, ed. Moshe Hershler (Jerusalem: Mekhon ha-Rav Hershler, 1992), Vol. 2, 591.

²³ See, for example, *Sefer Ḥasidim*, ed. Wistinetzki, 8-9 (#11); 131 (#455).

At about the same time that these comments were written in the Rhineland, the first extant manuscripts containing Shabbat Zemirot were penned in northern France.²⁴ The earliest of these are two unique iterations of the legal-liturgical work *Mahzor Vitry* that record the same three Hebrew poems identifiable as Shabbat Zemirot.²⁵ MS Moscow Guensburg 481, dated by Justine Isserles to the end of the 12th or very beginning of the 13th century, includes Shabbat Zemirot at the end of the manuscript. The precise role of these three songs is clarified in the other collection, JTS 8092, which is dated to c. 1204. After returning home from synagogue on Saturday afternoon, the manuscript's readers are instructed to begin the ritual meal by reciting the opening blessing known as *Kiddush*, blessing the bread, and

afterwards, they should eat half their meal and have brought before them fish and other delicacies. With these on the table, they should sing the song composed by the rabbi, the teacher, Shimon the son of the rabbi, the teacher, Yitzchak (may his memory be a blessing) and then the song composed by Dunash the son of Labrat and then the song composed by Rabbi Abraham ibn Ezra.²⁶

This note is followed by complete renderings of the three songs mentioned: *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom*, *Dror Yikra* and *Ki Eshamara Shabbat*. While these two manuscripts are the earliest evidence for a prescribed table-singing repertoire, the fact that they both contain the same three songs suggests that a specific repertoire had already taken root in Northern France. Over the course of the 13th century, five additional manuscripts of *Mahzor Vitry* and related works were copied that included a Shabbat Zemirot repertoire built around these three core songs. Since every manuscript of *Mahzor Vitry* contains a unique liturgical tradition that reflects the varying local practices in its own community, this cannot be disregarded as one community's local

²⁴ For the sake of readability of both the article and the footnotes, information about the provenance of the manuscripts discussed in this article can be found in Appendix 1.

²⁵ MS Moscow Guensburg, 481, fols. 334v-335r; MS New York Jewish Theological Seminary 8092, fol. 38r-v.

²⁶ MS New York Jewish Theological Seminary 8092, fol. 38r.

tradition.²⁷ Rather, the appearance of Shabbat Zemirot in the various *Maḥzor Vitry* manuscripts indicates that singing these songs was a known practice across multiple communities by the 13th century.

²⁷ I am indebted to Dr. Justine Isserles for sharing her pre-publication work on and description of the *Maḥzor Vitry* manuscript tradition. Justine Isserles, “Maḥzor Vitry: A Study of Liturgical-Halakhic Compendia from Medieval Franco-Germany,” *Jewish History* (2021) (forthcoming).

The Shabbat Zemirot contained in these early Northern French collections come from diverse sources. Their authors are well known Hebrew poets who lived in various regions of Jewish settlement in the 10th through 12th centuries. The three core songs were written by the Ashkenazic liturgical poet Shimon b. Yitzchak (d. 1015) [*Barukh Hashem Yom Yom*], the Sephardic Abraham ibn Ezra (1089-1164) [*Ki Eshmera Shabbat*] who left Spain to migrate around Europe and the Sephardic poet Dunash b. Labrat (10th c.) [*Dror Yikra*]. Throughout the Middle Ages, Shabbat Zemirot collections continued to include poems by a mix of Ashkenazi, Sephardic, and Italian poets. This integration of different poetic traditions supports Elisabeth Hollender's identification of the increasing importance of Sephardic poetry in the liturgies of France and Ashkenaz during the High Middle Ages.²⁸ Precedence, though, was generally given to the local region's poets. *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom*, for example, consistently appears first in the early northern French collections likely because of its Ashkenazic author who is reverently referred to as "our rabbi, the teacher" in the manuscript of *Mahzor Vitry* from 1204.²⁹

While many poems sung as Shabbat Zemirot in Northern Europe were composed by Sephardic liturgical poets, there are no explicit witnesses to these poems being similarly sung during Shabbat meals in Spain. In fact, there is no clear evidence of an established Shabbat Zemirot tradition in pre-expulsion Spain paralleling that which developed in other parts of Europe.³⁰ This, of course, does not mean that Spanish Jews were not singing during their meals, but rather that a structured practice with a defined repertoire of songs does not seem to have

²⁸ See Elisabeth Hollender "Adoption and Adaption" in *Entangled Histories*, eds. E. Baumgarten, R. M. Karras and K. Mesler (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2017), 248-262; Elisabeth Hollender, "Sefarad in Tzarfat: Sefardi and Sefardi-Style Piyyutim in MS Bernkastel-Kues 313" in *'His Pen and Ink Are a Powerful Mirror'*, eds. A. Bursi, S.J. Pearce and H. Zafer (Leiden: Brill, 2020), 94-117.

²⁹ Quoted above from MS New York Jewish Theological Seminary 8092, fol. 38v.

³⁰ Tova Beeri and Edwin Seroussi have suggested that the custom to sing around the table did not take root among Sephardic Jews until the 20th century. Tova Beeri and Edwin Seroussi, "Rabbi Israel Najara in Ashkenaz," *Kabbalah* 33 (2015), 72, n. 11.

taken shape there.³¹ The Sephardic poems sung around Shabbat tables in northern France and German-speaking lands during the Middle Ages migrated north, like so many other Sephardic poems, and were repurposed as Shabbat table songs.³²

Bearing the cautionary advice of historians of early music, one cannot assume that these written collections of Shabbat Zemirot constitute either the beginning or the entirety of Shabbat table-singing.³³ Given the cultural importance of communal singing, Jews were almost certainly singing in celebration of Shabbat before any written sources assigned specific songs to the occasion. The existence of a range of potential table-songs is evidenced by sources which recommend various genres, such as “psalms of praise” or “the works of the poets,” that families could sing around their tables.³⁴ Aaron b. Jacob of Lunel (14th century), for example, suggests Psalms 23, 24 and 104 as appropriate.³⁵ These recommendations suggest that medieval Jews had a storehouse of songs that they could call-upon when singing around their tables. Among these were likely orally transmitted songs, whether in Hebrew or the vernacular, known from the synagogue or the musically vibrant urban environment. While the primary evidence for Shabbat Zemirot are the extant instructions to sing specific songs, other songs which were never written down likely made up a significant portion of Shabbat table-singing throughout the Middle Ages. The question remains, though: Why were Jews singing at all?

³¹ Instructions found in the Zohar to sing songs on Shabbat around the table indicate that this was a known and practiced custom, even if the repertoire of songs remained undefined. Moshe Halamish, *Kabbalistic customs of Shabbat*, 342-3.

³² On the movement of poetry and others cultural content from Spain into France, see Avraham Grossman, *The Early Sages of France* (Jerusalem: Magnes Press, 2001), 554-71 [in Hebrew].

³³ John Haines warns that “equating all of medieval music activity with the surviving parchment record is like assuming that a future historian might obtain a fair idea of modern popular music by reading a handful of jazz fake books published in the early twenty-first century.” Haines, *Medieval Song*, 12-13.

³⁴ MS Oxford Bodleian Library Opp. 670, fols. 39v-40r. Quoted below.

³⁵ Aaron b. Jacob of Lunel, *Sefer 'rkhot Ḥayim: Inyinei Shabbat*, eds. S. Klein and Y. Klein (Jerusalem: Mekhon Yerushalyim, 1996), 295.

Why Sing?

Singing during Shabbat meals served several potential functions in medieval Jewish homes. On the most basic level, singing infused the Shabbat meal with joy. This role is both intuitive and richly attested to in the sources. According to *Sefer Ḥasidim*, singing Zemirot “fills one’s heart with joyousness in one’s love of God.”³⁶ Gershom Ha-gozer, a 13th-century practitioner of circumcision in Ashkenaz, describes singing Zemirot as necessary for fulfilling one’s obligation to celebrate the circumcision of a baby boy: “Accordingly, it is for the father of the boy to make joyousness and drinking on the day of his son's circumcision and they should sing Zemirot.”³⁷ Across Jewish society, singing was a sign of pious celebration, and it continued to function as such around the Shabbat table each week. On a more banal level, singing also helped pass the time.³⁸ On the day of rest in particular, Jews sought to engage in appropriate activities that would fill their time. Various rabbinic commentaries praise Jews for spending their days of rest engaged in holy activities in contrast to their gentile neighbors who pursued only drunken revelry.³⁹ Aside from praying and feasting, sources describe Jews spending Shabbat studying Torah and—to the chagrin of some rabbis—reading secular literature.⁴⁰ By reciting the

³⁶ *Sefer Ḥasidim*, ed. Wistinetzki, 216 (#815).

³⁷ Jacob Ha-gozer, *Sefer Zikhron brit la-rishonim*, ed. Y. Glasberg (Berlin: Itzkowski Press, 1892), 68.

³⁸ On medieval pastimes, see Paul Milliman, “Games and Pastimes” in *Handbook of Medieval Culture*, ed. A. Classen (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2015), 582-612. For a look at Jewish pastimes, see Israel Abrahams, *Jewish Life in the Middle Ages* (Philadelphia: Jewish Publication Society, 1993), 373-398.

³⁹ See, among others, Eleazar of Worms: “When the gentiles eat, and drink, and become drunk, they speak about fornication, just like Ahasuerus, and anger and disobey the holy word. Yet, Israel . . . even though they eat and drink, they praise you for their bounty . . . thereby at the afternoon [Shabbat] service, after we have eaten and drunk, we say ‘As for my prayer’ meaning that I am praying before you.” Eleazar b. Judah, *Perushei siddur*, Vol. 2, 581.

⁴⁰ On the reading of secular literature on Shabbat, Ephraim Urbach, *The Tosaphists* (Jerusalem: Mossad Bialik, 1980), Vol. 1, 325 [in Hebrew].

words of the famed Hebrew poets in the Shabbat Zemiroth, Jews could pass the day joyously and piously.⁴¹

During the 13th century, singing around the table also served a more practical, legalistic function. On Shabbat, Jews were strained by their obligation to eat three distinct ritual meals between sundown on Friday and sundown on Saturday. Even for those who had the necessary financial resources, short winter days made it challenging to hold two full meals on Saturday before the sun set. Consequently, some sought to split the meal that was held after morning prayers on Saturday so that it might be counted twice. Several Ashkenazic rabbis allowed their followers to do so by reciting the post-meal benediction between courses and then ritually beginning another meal.⁴² Several generations of French rabbinic authorities, however, rejected this practice.⁴³ Some French authorities did, however, offer an alternative means for splitting the meal: singing. This method is described in detail in a liturgical collection written in northern France at the beginning of the 13th century:

One should do this and he will fulfill his obligation for three ritual meals: eat your first meal [of the day] and cover the food with a cloth, recite the post-meal benediction . . . recite songs [זמירות] from the Psalms, such as ‘To the Lord is the earth and its fullness’ or other psalms of praise or the works of the poets, and afterwards wash one’s hands and recite the blessing over them [in order to begin a new meal] . . . While reciting the songs and Zemiroth, one loses concentration and therefore one needs to rewash their hands and then bless the bread and eat the second ritual meal [of the day] and as such they fulfill the obligation for three ritual meals on Shabbat.⁴⁴

⁴¹ On domestic singing as a pre-modern pastime, see Trocme-Latter, *The Singing of the Strasbourg Protestants*, 78-79.

⁴² Eleazar of Worms seems to allow it entirely. *Sefer ha-rokeach ha-gadol*, ed. S. Schneerson (Jerusalem: Otzer ha-Poskim, 1960), 43 (#54). Asher b. Yeḥiel (1250-1327) notes that his teachers would go from their second to third meal without any formal break only when the meal had continued late enough into the day. *Shut Ha-rosh*, ed. Y. S. Yudelov (Jerusalem: Mekhon Yerushalayim, 1994), 113 (22:4).

⁴³ *Sefer ha-pardes*, ed. H. L. Ehrenreich (Budapest: H. L. Ehrenreich, 1924), 195; Jacob b. Meir, *Sefer ha-yashar le-Rabenu Tam: Helek ha-Hidushim*, ed. S. S. Schlesinger (Jerusalem: Sifriyati, 1985), 392 (#298). The copy of *Maḥzor Vitry* from 1242 also cites this rejection, see MS London British Library Add. 27200, fol. 90r.

⁴⁴ MS Oxford Bodleian Library Opp. 670, fol. 40r. Printed in *Meorot rishonim*, ed. S. E. Stern (Jerusalem: Mekhon Yerushalayim, 2002), Vol. 1, 74.

According to this ruling, singing was the essential factor in splitting the Shabbat midday meal as it alone was deemed sufficiently distracting to demand the initiation of a new meal. This method of splitting the meal is referenced in two of the earliest collections of Shabbat Zemirot from Northern France. The copyists explicitly instruct that participants sing *in the middle of the meal*, almost certainly to take advantage of the leniency offered by the French rabbis.⁴⁵ While this understanding seems to have been rooted in northern France, Eleazar of Worms in the Rhineland acknowledged it as well. He observed that

after eating the warmed cooked foods, there are those who sing songs and praises to the Holy Blessed One on Shabbat and afterwards eat the conclusion of the meal, fish or poultry or fruit, so that there would be three ritual meals, one in the evening, one at midday and one as the conclusion [of that midday meal].⁴⁶

While he does not necessarily advocate it, Eleazar is clearly aware that “there are those who” rely on singing to fulfill their requirement for three Shabbat meals.

This explanation for singing was key in the early development of the Shabbat Zemirot tradition. Kenneth E. Berger has recently highlighted how novel understandings of prayers and rituals influence their spread and development.⁴⁷ By reinterpreting the common practice of table-singing as a mechanism to split the Shabbat afternoon meal into two, these rabbis shaped the development of Shabbat table-singing in northern France. For one, this understanding linked singing to the middle of the afternoon meal, the only time at which it took on a clear ritual function.⁴⁸ More importantly, this newfound ritual significance inspired standardization. The ascription of a ritual function to singing demanded that an appropriate repertoire of songs be

⁴⁵ MS New York Jewish Theological Seminary 8092, fol. 38r; MS London British Library Add. 27200, fol. 89r.

⁴⁶ Eleazar of Worms, *Sefer ha-rokeach ha-gadol*, 43 (#54)

⁴⁷ Kenneth E. Berger, *Tradition, Interpretation, and Change* (Cincinnati: Hebrew Union College Press, 2019), 11-12.

⁴⁸ For the lasting significance of this placement, see MS New York Jewish Theological Seminary 8092, fol. 38r; MS London British Library Add. 27200, fol. 89r; MS Paris Alliance Israélite Universelle 133H, fol. 133v; Yosef b. Moses, *Leket Yosher*, ed. Amichai Kinarti (Jerusalem: Mekhon Yerushalayim, 2010), Vol. 1, 72 (#24).

drafted. This could explain why, even though communal singing was likely common among Jews across medieval Europe, the first crafted repertoires of Shabbat Zemirot appeared in Northern France where table-singing was ascribed ritual significance.

This halakhic function can also explain an oddity in the original three songs established as Shabbat Zemirot in our earliest collections from Northern France. Unlike *Ki Eshmera Shabbat* and *Dror Yikra*, *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom* has no thematic relevance to Shabbat.⁴⁹ That such a song would be enshrined in the repertoire of Shabbat table-songs is rather surprising given that the lyrics of the other two core Shabbat Zemirot directly reflect the themes of the holy day. *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom*, however, does share some similarities with *Birkat Ha-mazon*, the grace after meals.⁵⁰ Traditionally, Jews conclude their meals by praising God for sustaining the hungry; Shimon b. Yitzchak, the poem's famed author, very similarly opens by blessing God for being the "strengtheners of the weak and shelter for the poor." In place of praising "the Lord the God because he took us out from the land of Egypt and redeemed us from the house of slavery," Shimon b. Yitzchak describes how God "magnified us; like these and those he added unto us." The connection between *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom* and *Birkat Ha-mazon* is emphasized in the earliest Shabbat Zemirot collections in which the three stanzas starting with "Bless the Lord for . . ." appear conspicuously at the start of the song.⁵¹ This organization allows the song to reflect the *Birkat Ha-mazon*, which is structured as a sequence of blessings that start with "Blessed are You, the Lord." Though not overtly relevant to Shabbat, *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom* parallels

⁴⁹ For similar discussion of the thematic links between the Shabbat Zemirot and Shabbat, see Beeri, Tova. "Zur Mi-Shelo Achalnu," 428.

⁵⁰ I am indebted to Professor Menachem Schmeltzer for pointing out this connection to me. Quotations come from *Liturgical Poems of R. Shim'on bar Yitshaq*, ed. A. M. Haberman (Jerusalem: Schocken, 1938), 181-183 [in Hebrew].

⁵¹ The variation in the order of the stanzas over the course of the Middle Ages is noted by Habermann.

Birkat Ha-mazon and was therefore codified as a Shabbat Zemer because its recitation was understood as the technical end of a meal.⁵²

The Spread of Shabbat Zemirot:

After the codification of several songs as Shabbat Zemirot, manuscripts containing them began to appear outside of Northern France.⁵³ We will trace the wider diffusion of this practice by following the production of these collections. The appearance of such collections of Shabbat Zemirot does not necessarily indicate the emergence of a new table-singing practice, which likely had already existed for centuries. Yet, these collections evidence the incremental spread of an established table-singing tradition from Northern France into Ashkenaz and Italy.⁵⁴ Since song collections frequently intermingle numerous liturgical poems and rarely provide indications as to the purpose of any particular one, identifying a set of songs as Shabbat Zemirot can be challenging. For the purposes of this study, the presence of the previously discussed three songs found in the earliest collections as well as that of the evening-time song *Kol Mekadesh* serve as indicators that the sequence of songs among which they appear was intended to be sung during Shabbat meals. These four songs do not constitute the complete repertoire of Shabbat Zemirot, but they mark a manuscript as containing Shabbat table-songs in northern France and Ashkenaz.

⁵² This is not to say that *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom* functioned as a poetic replacement for *Birkat Ha-mazon*, but only that the reflection of themes inspired its choice as poem sung at a time when one might expect *Birkat Ha-mazon*. On the custom to recite poetic versions of *Birkat Ha-mazon* in place of the actual prayer, see Avi Shmidman, “The Liturgical Function of Poetic Versions of the Grace After Meals” in *Ginzei Kedem 2*, ed. Robert Brody (Jerusalem: Mekhon Ben-Tsevi, 2006), pp. 45-102 [in Hebrew]. For the texts of these poems, see: Idem., “The Poems for the Grace after Meals from the Cairo Genizah: A Critical Edition,” Doctoral Dissertation (Bar Ilan University, 2009).

⁵³ On customs spreading from Ashkenaz to the rest of Europe, see Elisheva Baumgarten, *Practicing Piety in Medieval Ashkenaz* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2014), 12-13 and 216-217.

⁵⁴ Beeri suggests similarly that the popular Shabbat Zemer *Tzur Mishelo* originated in Northern France and radiated out through Ashkenaz into Italy. Tova Beeri, “Zur Mi-Shelo Achalnu,” 429-30.

Geographic spread, though, does not prove that the wider Jewish public was engaged in this practice. We must ask, then, how widespread was the singing of Shabbat Zemirot? The best indicators of the popularity are the genres of manuscripts used to collect the songs as well as their signs of use. While rabbinic commentary cannot always be relied upon for insights about life outside of the scholarly sphere, manuscript collections are windows into the experience of a wider range of Jews who were using them in their daily lives. This is especially true for Hebrew manuscripts, which Malachi Beit-Arié has argued were generally produced for the personal use of their owners.⁵⁵ One can, as a result, follow Virginia Reinburg in her study of Books of Hours and analyze the full set of known collections of Shabbat Zemirot as “artefacts” whose content, structure, and marginalia reveal the significance of these songs to everyday, medieval Jews.⁵⁶ By tracing the production of manuscripts containing Shabbat Zemirot and simultaneously examining how these collections were formatted and used, this section will demonstrate how the custom to sing specific Shabbat Zemirot flowered into a mainstay of Jewish life in Europe.

From Northern France and into Ashkenaz:

The earliest evidence for a structured Shabbat Zemirot custom is found in seven 13th-century northern French manuscripts, six of which are unique, localized editions of *Mahzor Vitry*.⁵⁷ In addition to the three songs discussed above, the pillar of the evening repertoire, *Kol Mekadesh*, and the popular daytime song, *Barukh El Elyon*, were among various others introduced in northern France.⁵⁸ The fact that the appearance of Shabbat Zemirot was restricted

⁵⁵ Malachi Beit-Arié, *Unveiled Faces of Medieval Hebrew Books* (Jerusalem: Magnes Press, 2003), 62-64; Idem., “The Individualistic Nature of the Hebrew Medieval Book Production and Consumption,” *Zion* 65.4 (2000): 441-451 [in Hebrew].

⁵⁶ Virginia Reinburg, *French Books of Hours* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012), 7-8.

⁵⁷ For a discussion of medieval French Hebrew liturgy and its manuscript tradition, see Colette Sirat, “Les manuscrits liturgiques des juifs en France médiévale,” *Revue des études juives*, 174:3-4 (2015), 325-357.

⁵⁸ MS London British Library Add. 27200, fol. 72r-v.

to the elite, rabbinic work *Maḥzor Vitry* may suggest that during the 13th century this repertoire did not yet have cultural traction among the wider population in northern France. It would be questionable, however, to draw conclusions since alternative prayer books, and especially personal prayer books, were still rare among Jews at the time.⁵⁹ It is also possible that smaller, more accessible liturgical manuscripts containing these songs, pointing to widespread dissemination, did exist in northern France but have not survived to our day. There is one indication that Shabbat Zemirot had some level of popular penetration. A scribal note in a copy of *Maḥzor Vitry* from 1241 instructs that circumcision songs should be sung to the tune of *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom*.⁶⁰ That a scribe would reference the tune of a Shabbat Zemer suggests that the song was known and popular in his and, probably, other northern French communities. Even with this glance at everyday Jewish musical life, it is impossible to determine whether the other Shabbat Zemirot had taken root in the homes of a wide subsection of northern French Jews.

During the 14th century, a period of persecution and expulsion for French Jews, we have almost no direct witnesses to the development of the tradition in northern France.⁶¹ Manuscripts containing the core Shabbat Zemirot introduced in France do, however, appear in Ashkenaz. It is clear from *Sefer Ḥasidim* and Eleazar of Worms that a custom to sing around the Shabbat table was known in the Rhineland already in the 13th century. These comments provide no information about what was being sung, though. Our earliest extant manuscripts containing specific Shabbat

⁵⁹ Israel Ta-Shma, *The Early Ashkenazic Prayer* (Jerusalem: Magnes Press, 2003), 26-32 [in Hebrew]. On Hebrew manuscripts during the 12th and the start of the 13th Century, Judith Olszowy-Schlanger, "Hebrew Books" in *The European Book in the Twelfth Century*, eds. E. Kwakkel and R. Thomson (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018), 159-174.

⁶⁰ *Maḥzor Vitry*, ed. S. Horowitz (Nürnberg: Bulka, 1892), 627 (#505). MS London British Library Add. 27201, fol. 184v.

⁶¹ On the movement of northern French liturgical customs, see Colette Sirat, "Les manuscrits liturgiques des juifs en France médiévale"; Ivan Marcus, "Why Did Medieval Northern French Jewry (Ṣarfāt) Disappear?" in *Jews, Christians, and Muslims in Medieval and Early Modern Times*, eds. A. E. Franklin, R. E. Margariti, M. Rustow, and U. Simonsohn (Leiden: Brill, 2014), 99-117.

table-songs were produced sometime around the turn of the 14th century.⁶² The core repertoire known from Northern France was copied frequently in Ashkenaz during the 14th and 15th centuries. By the middle of the 15th century, this repertoire of songs had spread eastward across German speaking Jewish communities. In Wiener Neustadt, Austria, Yosef b. Moses mentions that his teacher, Israel Isserlein (1390-1460), would sing several Shabbat Zemirot that also appear in the earliest collections from Northern France.⁶³ While we have relatively few additional rabbinic observations or comments about the singing of Shabbat Zemirot in German-speaking lands during the 14th and 15th centuries, the manuscript evidence demonstrates clearly that the custom and repertoire were spreading.

Each of the Shabbat Zemirot recorded in northern French manuscripts found new homes in Ashkenazic collections. This is not to say, though, that the repertoire remained static during its migration. Rather, many new songs were introduced and made Ashkenazic collections substantially larger than their predecessors. While northern French works contain between three and seven songs, it is common to find twice that number in collections from German-speaking communities.⁶⁴ Some of the songs introduced in this expanded repertoire were *Yom Zeh Mekhubad* and *Menuha Ve-simḥa* which quickly became staples after their initial appearance in the 14th and 15th centuries, respectively.

While all the songs known in Northern France found their way into Ashkenazic collections, the manuscripts into which they were copied were entirely different from their northern French predecessors. Several collections from German-speaking lands are large

⁶² For a list of these early collections, see Appendix 1.

⁶³ Yosef b. Moses, *Leket Yosher*, Vol. 1, 72. On Isserlein, see Kinarti's introduction as well as Shlomo Eidelberg, *Jewish Life in Austria in the XVth Century* (Philadelphia: Jewish Publication Society, 1962), 38-59.

⁶⁴ For example, both MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina 1912 and MS Modena Biblioteca Estense Universitaria a.U.7.10 contain at least 15 songs.

Mahzorim that, like *Mahzor Vitry*, contain a complete account of a community's liturgical practice.⁶⁵ See, for example, one of the earliest Ashkenazic collections dated to the 13th or 14th century; MS London British Library Add. 27556 is made up of 188 folios (225x168mm) and contains—in addition to the Shabbat Zemirot—prayers for Shabbat, holidays, and ritual occasions, as well as various rabbinic commentaries and texts. Most collections of Shabbat Zemirot from German-speaking lands were, however, not this weighty. Instead, as was suggested by Avraham Fraenkel, they are typically smaller and more practical liturgical collections.⁶⁶ Many are collections of Hebrew songs for various occasions. See, for example, MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina 1931 which has 78 folios (150x110mm) and contains solely songs for various festivals.⁶⁷ In these songbooks, Shabbat Zemirot are generally singled out as their own unit, but also appear intermingled with songs for weddings and other occasions.⁶⁸ Other collections were smaller, domestic-oriented prayer-books that appeared during the 15th and 16th centuries. For example, a late 15th-century manuscript held by the Vatican Library has 52 folios (119x107mm)

⁶⁵ MS Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana ebr. 322; MS Giessen Universitätsbibliothek 742; MS Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana ebr. 323.

⁶⁶ Avraham Fraenkel, "Ha-zemer al hatzalat Worms v-zman chiburo shel 'Maoz Tzur,'" 15.

⁶⁷ See also, MS Leipzig Universitätsbibliothek B.H. duod. 43, fols. 38r-v & 43r-45v.

⁶⁸ Medieval Shabbat and wedding singing were linked in both Ashkenaz and Italy. See the Shabbat Zemirot in MS Oxford Bodleian Opp 59; MS Leipzig Universitätsbibliothek B.H. duod. 43; MS Rome Biblioteca Casanatense 1965, fols. 10v & 35r. For a specific example, see the song *Shlach Maheira Goel* which is marked in one manuscript as a song for weddings, but occasionally appears among the Shabbat Zemirot. MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina 1931, fol. 18v. Songs were similarly shared between the wedding and end-of-Shabbat repertoires. See Fudeman, *Vernacular Voices*, 128.

that contain table prayers, Shabbat songs, and various other domestic liturgical items.⁶⁹

Figure 2 Shabbat Zemer from an Ashkenaz Songbook dated to 1300 (MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina, 1931, 19v-20r)

The appearance of Shabbat Zemiroth in these more accessible manuscript genres suggests that during the 14th and 15th centuries, the songs were being sung by a wider Jewish audience. Such practical liturgical collections would have been used as part of the quotidian ritual lives of many Jews and not just by the scholarly elite.⁷⁰ Isaac b. Moses of Vienna (1200-1270) indicates that a wide range of Jews relied on songbooks when he remarks that, in his region, Jews would sit around the table on Friday evenings after a wedding and sing “from songbooks.”⁷¹ Such works would have been accessible and helpful to the broad swath of the Jewish community

⁶⁹ MS Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana ebr. 328.

⁷⁰ For example, individuals may have brought such smaller codices to synagogue to recite the Torah portion along with the cantor. Judith Olszowy-Schlanger, “Hebrew Books,” 173, n. 32.

⁷¹ Isaac b. Moses of Vienna, *Sefer Or Zaru'a*, Vol. 2, 42.

capable of reading Hebrew, even those without any substantive education in rabbinic literature.⁷² This is in stark contrast to the large, weighty manuscripts in which we find Shabbat Zemirot from 13th-century northern France and which would have been owned and used only by the most wealthy and scholarly Jews. In line with Beit-Arié's observation that most Hebrew manuscripts were made according to the needs of their owners, we can conclude that these shorter and more accessible works closely reflect the quotidian liturgical practices of wider Jewish society.⁷³ The fact that Shabbat Zemirot were included in such works points to their growing popularity in German-speaking lands.⁷⁴

Further indication of popular interest in these songs are the many manuscripts into which Shabbat Zemirot were added by later hands.⁷⁵ Since books were prohibitively expensive, many people inscribed those they already owned with texts to which they wanted to have immediate access.⁷⁶ In a mid to late 13th-century *Maḥzor*, one finds the first few lines of *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom* scribbled in by a later hand.⁷⁷ In a 14th-century Ashkenazic song book, two songs, *Yom Zeh Mekhubad* and *Kol Mekadesh*, were added to empty folios.⁷⁸ Because *Yom Zeh Mekhubad* was a later addition to the Shabbat Zemirot repertoire, a user probably added it to keep the collection up-to-date. While it is difficult to date and locate later additions with certainty, the

⁷² Ephraim Kanarfogel, "Prayer, Literacy and Literary memory in the Jewish Communities of Medieval Europe" in *Jewish Studies at the Crossroads of Anthropology and History: Authority, Diaspora, Tradition*, eds. R. S. Boustán, O. Kosansky and M. Rustow (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2011), 251-270.

⁷³ Malachi Beit-Arié, *Unveiled Faces of Medieval Hebrew Books*, 62-64; Idem., "The Individualistic Nature of the Hebrew Medieval Book Production and Consumption," 441-451.

⁷⁴ Though it seems likely that the singing of Shabbat Zemirot was gaining greater traction in Germany, we do not have enough material from the 14th century to effectively compare the popularity of the custom in Germany and Northern France. It is possible that Shabbat Zemirot were also included by French Jews in small works that simply did not survive to our day.

⁷⁵ In the list of manuscripts containing Shabbat Zemirot found in the index, the reader will find manuscripts with songs added by a later hand marked with an asterisk (*).

⁷⁶ Most interest in additions to medieval books focuses on scholarly notes and citations. Erik Kwakkel, *Books Before Print* (Leeds: ARC Humanities Press, 2018), 120-133. On additions to liturgical books by everyday readers, see Reinburg, *French Books of Hours*, 7-8 and 81-83.

⁷⁷ MS Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana ebr. 322, fol. 69r.

⁷⁸ MS Leipzig Universitätsbibliothek B.H. duod. 43, fol. 38r-v.

tendency for owners to add Shabbat Zemirot to their books suggests that they wanted to have easy access to these songs and were likely regularly singing them.

Into Italy:

The spread of Shabbat Zemirot did not restrict itself to German-speaking lands. At the end of the 14th century, *Sefer Minhag Tov*, an anonymous collection of pious practices that was composed in Italy, instructed that one should serenade God during the Shabbat meals: “It is a good custom to sing on Shabbat evening and day, each person at their table in order to honor the Shabbat and to tell of the grandeur of Shabbat and how dear it is before God.”⁷⁹ While it is likely that table-singing was common among Italian Jews by this time, *Sefer Minhag Tov* is less indicative of its place of composition in Italy than of its author’s roots in Northern France and Ashkenaz.⁸⁰ A structured Shabbat Zemirot practice did, though, take root and flourish in Italy. By the end of the 14th century, a specific repertoire of Shabbat table-songs appeared in manuscripts copied in Italy. These songs are generally assigned by their accompanying paratexts to the start of the Shabbat meal, before the recitation of Kiddush.⁸¹

The exact origin of the Italian Shabbat Zemirot tradition is unclear. It is possible that one finds in Italy a remnant of the northern French Shabbat Zemirot practice which, along with various French liturgical traditions, took root in Italy after the various expulsions of Jews from

⁷⁹ *Sefer Minhag Tov*, ed. M. Weiss, in *Ha-Zofeh le-Hokhmat Yisrael* 13 (Budapest, 1929), 228-229.

⁸⁰ *Sefer Minhag Tov* is believed to have been composed in northern Italy sometime around 1275 by a student of the French Tosafists. The practices recorded in his work reveal heavy Ashkenazic and French influence. Ephraim Kanarfogel, *Peering Through the Lattices* (Detroit: Wayne State University Press, 2000), 45-46, n. 34.

⁸¹ All the Shabbat Zemirot in Italian manuscripts have been indexed by Peter Sh. Lehnardt. He, though, classifies most as liturgical poems for “Friday evening prayers,” presumably, in the synagogue. While the Italian collections do not always provide paratextual instructions, those that do make clear that these songs were to be recited in the home in the context of the meal. See, for example, MS Cambridge University Library Add. 491.1, fol. 9v and MS London British Library Or. 13525, fol. 44r. Peter Sh. Lehnardt, “Studies in the Emergence of the Tradition of Hebrew Liturgical Poetry in Italy,” PhD Dissertation (Ben-Gurion University, 2006), 64-65 [in Hebrew].

France.⁸² This interpretation is suggested by several collections from northern Italy that contain *Dror Yikra* and *Ki Eshmera Shabbat*, two of the core *Zemirot* from the northern French repertoire, without any distinctively Italian additions.⁸³ This link to northern France is strengthened by the fact that at least one of these was also copied in a northern French hand.⁸⁴ At the same time, the practice that took shape in German-speaking lands also shaped the Italian custom. The fact that the earliest manuscript evidence for Italian Shabbat *Zemirot* comes from the end of the 14th century in northern Italy and includes some popular Ashkenazic Shabbat *Zemirot* suggests that the custom was influenced by the scores of German Jews immigrating to northern Italy to escape expulsion and economic persecution.⁸⁵ We see that at least some immigrants from German-speaking lands brought this custom and its repertoire with them in a 15th-century manuscript in which a clearly Ashkenazic Shabbat *Zemirot* repertoire was copied in an Italian book-hand.⁸⁶ The marginal notes written into a 15th-century Ashkenazic collection of Shabbat *Zemirot* by a user in Italy demonstrates that these separate Shabbat *Zemirot* traditions—Italian and Ashkenazi—existed simultaneously in Italy.⁸⁷ Though these links do not suggest the full transfer of a previous Shabbat *Zemirot* tradition into Italy, they show that the practice popular in northern France and Ashkenaz found a home in Italy and shaped the table-singing custom there.

⁸² On the French liturgical customs that survived in northern Italy and are known as *Minhag APaM*, see Colette Sirat, "Les manuscrits liturgiques des juifs en France médiévale", 340-341; Daniel Goldschmidt, "Postscript and Reconsiderations on the *Mahzor* of Asti, Fossano and Moncalvo" in Daniel Goldschmidt, *On Jewish Liturgy* (Jerusalem: Magnes Press, 1978), 80-121 [in Hebrew].

⁸³ MS Cambridge University Library Add. 2580, fol. 2r; MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina 1721, fols. 2r-3r.

⁸⁴ MS Budapest Library of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences Kaufmann A 370, 757-758.

⁸⁵ On Jewish immigrants to northern Italy at the end of the 14th century, see Alessandra Veronese, "Ashkenazic Immigrants in Northern Italy and their Relations with the Italian Jewish Population, c. 1380-1420" in *The Jews of Europe around 1400: Disruption, Crisis, and Resilience*, eds. L. Clemens and C. Cluse (Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2018), 157-172.

⁸⁶ MS Modena Biblioteca Estense Universitaria a.U.7.10, fols. 1r-10v.

⁸⁷ See MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina 2231, fol. 20r for a marginal note which explains that a certain *Zemer* sung by Ashkenazic Jews was not sung by Italian Jews.

Regardless of its external influences, a Shabbat Zemirot tradition took shape in Italy that was different than that found in either Ashkenaz or northern France.⁸⁸ On a paratextual level, Italian collections distinguish themselves by describing their Shabbat table-songs as “*Piyyutim*,” a more general term for liturgical poetry, as opposed to “Zemirot.”⁸⁹ More notable is the fact that songs appearing in Italian collections are very different from those of northern France and Ashkenaz. In comparison to the tens of songs found in some Ashkenazic collections, Italian manuscripts generally have about four.⁹⁰ Only two of these, *Ki Eshmera Shabbat* and *Yom Zeh Mekhubad*, appear in earlier collections. The other core songs of the Italian tradition were written by the Italian poet, Daniel b. Yehiel Anav (14th century).⁹¹ Overall then, Shabbat Zemirot collections from Italy are smaller, less diverse, and distinctively Italian compared to their earlier counterparts. These differences mean that though the Italian Shabbat Zemirot tradition may have been informed by its predecessors, it developed its own unique character as well.⁹²

⁸⁸ While different liturgical rites were practiced across Italy, regional distinctions are difficult to parse. This author has not been able to decipher any distinctive local traditions in the Shabbat Zemirot from Italy. For background on Italian liturgy, see Ruth Langer, *Cursing the Christians? A History of the Birkat HaMinim* (Oxford, 2012), 206-211.

⁸⁹ See, for example, MS Rome Biblioteca Casanatense 1965, fol. 10v; MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina 3132, fol. 36r; National Library of Israel, Film Number: MSS-D 1686, fols. 59r & 60r. Compare this with manuscripts from Ashkenaz which refer to the songs as “Shabbat Zemirot.” MS Giessen Universitätsbibliothek 742, frag. 10r. There were deviations from this trend. One northern French collection refers to the Shabbat Zemirot as “*Shirim*,” (MS Paris Alliance Israélite Universelle 133H, fol. 133v) and an Italian collection calls them “*heiruzim*” (MS Vienna Österreichischen Nationalbibliothek Hebr. 87, 116v).

⁹⁰ One Italian manuscript cements these four specific Zemirot as pillars of the Italian custom when it introduces them as “the four poems which it is the custom to sing on Shabbat.” MS Rome Biblioteca Casanatense 1965, fol. 10v.

⁹¹ Davidson links each of these Italian Shabbat Zemirot to Daniel b. Yehiel of Montalcino. Israel Davidson, *Thesaurus of Mediaeval Hebrew Poetry*, vol. 4 (New York, 1933), 378. Though a son of the famed Anav family, little has been written about Daniel. Schirmann includes one of his poems in his collection of *Piyyutim* from Italy, *Mivhar ha-shirah ha-‘Ivrit be-Italyah*, ed. H. Schirmann (Berlin: Schocken, 1934), 169.

⁹² While scholars have emphasized the social and ritual segregation of the Jewish communities in Northern Italy, the spread of the Shabbat Zemirot in the area points to at least some level of interaction and cultural transmission. On liturgical developments caused by Ashkenazic immigration to Northern Italy, see Lucia Raspe, “The Migration of German Jews into Italy and the Emergence of Local Rites of Selihot Recitation” in *The Jews of Europe around 1400*, 173-192.

Given that Benjamin Richler has called Italy the “Breadbasket of Hebrew Manuscripts,” it is unsurprising that less than two centuries worth of extant Shabbat Zemirot collections from Italy outnumber those from northern France and Ashkenaz combined over the entire period of the Middle Ages.⁹³ These Italian manuscript collections are just as diverse as those from Ashkenaz. Some manuscripts containing Italian Shabbat Zemirot are large *Maḥzorim* which hold the complete liturgy.⁹⁴ Most, though, are smaller songbooks and domestic prayer-books. See, for example, two 15th-century prayer-books which, alongside Shabbat Zemirot, include various prayers important for domestic life such as the post-meal benediction, table-rituals for Shabbat and holidays, as well as bedtime prayers.⁹⁵ The frequent appearance of Shabbat Zemirot in these accessible and practical domestic prayer-books suggests that the Italian repertoire of songs had penetrated a wide swath of Jewish society.⁹⁶ This is suggested by a 15th-century Roman-rite siddur which remarks that it was customary “in numerous places” to sing those Shabbat Zemirot.⁹⁷ The addition of Shabbat Zemirot to manuscripts by later hands also points to a reading-public invested in having access to these songs. One user added *Ki Eshmera Shabbat* and *Menuḥa Ve-simḥa* to the end of a *Siddur* penned in 1473.⁹⁸ Another fit the song *Dishanta* into the margins of a 15th-century liturgical collection.⁹⁹ Even manuscripts whose content lacked any thematic connection to domestic or Shabbat liturgy could be amended to include the

⁹³ Benjamin Richler, “Italy, the ‘Breadbasket’ of Hebrew Manuscripts” in *The Italia Judaica Jubilee Conference*, eds. S. Simonsohn and J. Shatzmiller (Leiden: Brill, 2013), 137-138.

⁹⁴ See MS Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana ebr. 594 which contains the complete Roman-rite on 326 folios, with only four folios dedicated to Shabbat Zemirot.

⁹⁵ MS Rome Biblioteca Casanatense 1965 and MS Paris Bibliothèque Nationale hebr. 601.

⁹⁶ On the impetus behind the production of Hebrew manuscripts in Italy, Malachi Beit-Arié, “Commissioned and Owner-Produced Manuscripts in the Sephardi Zone and Italy in the Thirteenth–Fifteenth Centuries,” in *The Late Medieval Hebrew Book in the Western Mediterranean*, ed. J. del Barco (Leiden: Brill, 2015), 15-27.

⁹⁷ MS Cambridge University Library Add. 491:1, fol. 9v.

⁹⁸ MS Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, Ross. 357, fols. 106v-107v.

⁹⁹ MS Paris Bibliothèque nationale hebr. 601, fol. 37r.

Zemiroth. On one of the opening folios of a 1399 copy of the classic Halakhic work *Sefer Mitzvot Katan*, an owner copied *Ki Eshmera Shabbat* and *Dror Yikra*, along with a few other prayers.¹⁰⁰

¹⁰⁰ MS Cambridge University Library Add. 2580, fol. 2r.

Figure 3 A 15th-century Italian Shabbat Zemirot collection with a song added into the margins. (MS BNF Hebreu 601, 37r)

ד שבת

יום זה מבורך מכל ימים כי בו שבת צור עולמים

קודם ברכת המזון אומר זה

עכא ועד אה

צודר מטלו אכלנו	ברכו אמוני
שב עננו והוה דנו	כרבר יי
הזן את עולמו	רענינו אבינו
אכלנו את לחמו	ויינו שתינו
על פן נודה לשמו	נהללו בפנינו
אמרנו וענינו	אין קדוש פני
צור מטלו אכלנו	פברדי ימדי
רחם בחסדך	על עמך צדינו
ועל מטבן כבודך	זבל תקוה יוננו
ופי דוד עבודך	יבנו ויבנו יוננו
רוח אפינו	משית יי
צודר מטלו אכלנו	השכ גלות א
	שוכ עלינו
	כרח פיס
	וחדיו ימם תמיס
	שכנו יעקב עוסק ירחי לא
	יסף ולא יבא עור שמיני
	ד שבת

The Social Life of Shabbat Zemirot

While these manuscript collections indicate that Shabbat Zemirot were a part of medieval Jewish life generally, a closer read of the evidence illuminates the place they held within the communities and families who were singing them. In medieval Ashkenaz, it was considered praiseworthy to know and to sing pious songs. We see this in Eleazar of Worms' praise for his wife and two daughters for having learned and sung "Zemirot," likely referring to para-liturgical poems generally.¹⁰¹ While this example comes from 1196, before almost any Shabbat Zemirot collections were copied, the frequent references to communal singing across Hebrew sources indicate that this interest in learning and singing pious songs continued throughout the Middle Ages. But how did Jews learn such songs?¹⁰² While the numerous extant collections of Shabbat Zemirot depict the spread and expansion of the written repertoire, expensive manuscripts likely would not have been part of most Jews' musical education. Even the relatively accessible songbooks and domestic prayer-books would only have been available to wealthy community members. Another possibility for textual transmission was via low-quality "booklets" that provided personal access to the liturgy.¹⁰³ Ephraim Kanarfogel has recently described these as "relatively small units of texts copied in a somewhat rudimentary fashion,

¹⁰¹ *Gezerot Ashkenaz ve-Tsarfat*, ed. A. Habermann (Jerusalem: Tarshish, 1945), 165-6. For background, Judith R. Baskin, "Dolce of Worms: The Lives and Deaths of an Exemplary Medieval Jewish Woman and her Daughters" in *Judaism in Practice: From the Middle Ages through the Early Modern Period*, ed. L. Fine (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2001), 429-437.

¹⁰² This question has received ample attention from music historians interested in monks learning to chant the Psalms, but little attention has been paid to the method by which lay people learned to sing. Anna Maria Busse Berger, *Medieval Music and the Art of Memory* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2005); Susan Boynton, "Training for the Liturgy as a Form of Monastic Education" in *Medieval Monastic Education*, eds. George Ferzoco and Carolyn Muessig (London: Leicester University Press, 2000), 7-20; Anna Maria Busse Berger, "Teaching and Learning Music" in *The Cambridge History of Medieval Music*, eds. M. Everist and T. F. Kelly (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018), vol. 1, 475-499.

¹⁰³ For background on the physical structure of these booklets, Pamela Robinson, "The format of books – books, booklets and rolls" in *The Cambridge History of the Book in Britain*, eds. N. J. Morgan and R. M. Thomson (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008), 50-52.

which were then gathered in a kind of a limp or flimsy wrapper rather than more carefully bound as a codex.”¹⁰⁴ Because of their inferior quality, such pamphlets were financially more accessible but also rarely survived until today. Isaac of Vienna may be referring to these “booklets” when he observes, as discussed above, that many in his community would sing Shabbat Zemirot from “song books” on Friday evenings.¹⁰⁵

More important than written texts, though, was the oral transmission of Shabbat Zemirot. Kanarfogel and others have emphasized that it was common, especially in Northern France and Ashkenaz, to memorize the regular liturgy.¹⁰⁶ As songs sung every week, Shabbat Zemirot would have similarly been learned by heart. Yet, because these liturgical poems do not appear in the synagogue liturgy, medieval Jews would have been exposed to the Shabbat Zemirot primarily in their homes, specifically by their parents.¹⁰⁷ In his praise of his youngest martyred daughter, Eleazar of Worms describes the transmission of paraliturgical poetry from parent to child. He writes that his daughter learned Zemirot not from any book, but from her mother.¹⁰⁸ While Eleazar’s wife Dulce is not necessarily representative of medieval Jewish women, this points to a trend of parental education highlighted in other sources as well.¹⁰⁹ Jews may have also been

¹⁰⁴ Ephraim Kanarfogel, “Evidence for the Availability of Prayer Texts for the Laity in Ashkenaz during the Twelfth and Thirteenth Centuries,” Conference paper given at *Literacy and Everyday Culture among Medieval Jews, Christians, and Muslims* (Jerusalem, February 19th, 2020). The author would like to thank Professor Kanarfogel for sharing his paper.

¹⁰⁵ Isaac b. Moses of Vienna, *Sefer or Zaru'a*, vol. 2, 43.

¹⁰⁶ Ephraim Kanarfogel, “Prayer, Literacy and Literary Memory,” 251-270.

¹⁰⁷ The oral transmission of Shabbat Zemirot in the home took multiple forms. Children would have learned via active parental instruction, regular participation in singing, familial discussion of the rituals and from the practices of visitors. This parallels the oral transmission of liturgical customs within monasteries. Susan Boynton, “Oral Transmission of Liturgical Practice in the Eleventh-Century Customaries of Cluny” in *Understanding Monastic Practices of Oral Communication*, ed. S. Vanderputten (Turnhout: Brepols, 2011), 67-83.

¹⁰⁸ *Gezerot Ashkenaz ve-Tsarfat*, 165-6. On mothers as domestic educators, see Michael Clanchy, “Did Mothers Teach their Children to Read?” in *Motherhood, Religion, and Society in Medieval Europe, 400-1400*, eds. C. Leyser and L. Smith (Burlington: Ashgate, 2011), 129-153. For a view that emphasizes the father’s responsibility in Jewish religious education, see Elisheva Baumgarten, *Mothers and Children* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2012), 161-163.

¹⁰⁹ For Jewish parental attempts to religiously educate their children, see Ephraim Kanarfogel, *Jewish Education and Society in the High Middle Ages* (Detroit: Wayne State University Press, 1992), 36-41; Elisheva Baumgarten,

teaching children these songs not just to be sung but also as an education tool. In 1510, the Jews of Frankfurt attempted to evade Christian confiscation of their so-called “*Miros* books” by claiming that they were used only for educating children.¹¹⁰ It is very likely that these “*Miros* books” were actually collections of Zemirot (pronounced “Zmiros” in Ashkenaz) and that, like Christians and the liturgical texts in their Books of Hours, Jews were using them to teach their children how to read.¹¹¹ The practice of parents teaching children songs may be hinted at in *Mah Yedidut*, a popular Shabbat Zemer introduced in Ashkenaz in the 14th century. The song links teaching children with singing songs in its list of praiseworthy activities for the Shabbat: “Passing thoughts are permitted [on Shabbat] along with making matches for girls / so too to teach a child a book, to recite praises in melodies / and to meditate on fine words at every place and gathering.”¹¹² Whether through formal parental instruction or regular passive listening, the center of Shabbat Zemirot education would have been the home.¹¹³

“Religious Education of Children in Medieval Jewish Society” in *Essays on Medieval Childhood: Responses to Recent Debates*, ed. J. Rosenthal (Sheffield: Shaun Tyas, 2007), 54-72.

¹¹⁰ *Regesten zur Geschichte der Juden in der Reichsstadt Frankfurt am Main von 1401–1519*, ed. D. Andernacht (Hannover: Hahnsche Buchhandlung, 1996), Vol. 3, 958 (#3656). For background, see Avner Shamir, “Johannes Pfefferkorn and the Dual Form of the Confiscation Campaign” in *Revealing the Secrets*, 61-76.

¹¹¹ On Christians teaching children to read from Books of Hours, see Virginia Reinburg, *French Books of Hours*, 100-108.

¹¹² See the earliest extant copy of this Zemer, MS Leipzig Universitätsbibliothek B.H. duod. 43, fol. 43r.

¹¹³ The oral transmission of the Shabbat Zemirot within the home suggests that both boys and girls would learn to sing, though differences may have existed in understanding. On difference in male and female participation in communal singing, see Fudeman, “They have ears, but do not hear,” 542-567; Avraham Grossman, *Pious and Rebellious: Jewish Women in Medieval Europe* (Waltham, 2004), 167-170 and 180-184. No medieval source describes female participation in Shabbat tale-singing. Katrin Kogman-Appel has collected artistic evidence for the substantive involvement of women in the medieval Passover Seder table-ritual that could indicate similar involvement in Shabbat table-practice. Katrin Kogman-Appel, “Portrayals of Women with Books: Female (Il)literacy in Medieval Jewish Culture” in *Reassessing the Roles of Women as 'Makers' of Medieval Art and Architecture*, ed. T. Martin (Leiden: Brill, 2012), 525-563. It is only at the turn of the 17th century that we have clear evidence of women singing Shabbat Zemirot. Yosef Yuspa Hahn, *Yosef Ometz*, eds. A. Kinarti and Y. Katan (Shaalavim: Mekhon Shlomo Oman, 2016), 177.

In addition to the text of the songs, the melodies to which they were sung were also transmitted orally.¹¹⁴ Since medieval musical notation was not part of the Jewish cultural sphere, communities developed various means for transmitting tunes. In several collections, one finds ekphonic notation, comparable to that in early monastic song books, adorning the Shabbat Zemirot. Instead of describing the music as modern notation does, these markings “served as a reminder of the melodies for those who already knew them by heart.”¹¹⁵ Beyond indicating the existence of communal melodies, such notation points to the continued centrality of orality even for this written liturgical tradition.

Figure 4 Ekphonic notation over the 6 syllables preceding the last 5 syllables of each stanza (MS JTS 8092, 38v)

¹¹⁴ Avraham Fraenkel, “Ha-zemer al hatzalat Worms v-zman chiburo shel ‘Maoz Tzur,’” 15. On the place and importance of tunes for medieval Hebrew liturgy and songs, see Colette Sirat, “Les manuscrits liturgiques des juifs en France médiévale”, *Revue des études juives*, 174:3-4 (2015), pp. 338-9; *Sefer Hasidim*, ed. Wistinetzki, 8-9 (#11) & 207 (#817). Additionally, see how in 16th-century Frankfurt it was only deemed appropriate to sing Shabbat Zemirot to somber tunes during mournful periods of the year. Hahn, *Yosef Ometz*, 171.

¹¹⁵ Susan Boynton, “Oral Transmission of Liturgical Practice,” 72-73.

Many Hebrew liturgical manuscripts provide more explicit instructions by including specific guidance on which melodies to use with certain prayers.¹¹⁶ This was also the case with Shabbat Zemirot. For example, the previously discussed note from the *Mahzor Vitry* manuscript dated to 1241 instructs that circumcision songs be sung to the tune of *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom*, implying that that the community had a specific tune for that Zemer.¹¹⁷ Evidence from Italy indicates that Jews there were similarly singing various songs to the clearly well-known tunes of Shabbat Zemirot.¹¹⁸ It seems that these melodies were passed down through the generations, though to what extent they remained consistent over time is impossible to know. One manuscript dated to the 13th or 14th century contains marginal notes instructing that three songs, including *Al Ahavatekha* and *Ki Eshmera Shabbat*, should be sung to the same, unknown tune.¹¹⁹ A collection of Shabbat Zemirot copied in northern Italy in 1516, almost three centuries later, similarly instructs that the song *Al Ahavatekha* should be sung to the tune of *Ki Eshmera Shabbat*.¹²⁰ As we have no written music from medieval Jewish communities, interpreting the musical content of either the quasi-notation or named tunes is impossible. Yet, the identification of known melodies linked to table-singing indicate that Jews were orally passing along tunes for their Shabbat Zemirot.¹²¹

¹¹⁶ Examples of this abound. For some, see Sarit Shalev-Eyni, “The Aural-Visual Experience,” 194-195.

¹¹⁷ *Mahzor Vitry*, ed. S. Horowitz, 627 (#506). MS London British Library Add. 27201, fol. 184v.

¹¹⁸ Claudia Rosenzweig, “Rhymes To Sing and Rhymes To Hang Up: Some Remarks on a Lamoon in Yiddish By Elye Bokher (Venice 1514)” in *The Italia Judaica Jubilee Conference*, eds. S. Simonsohn and J. Shatzmiller (Leiden: Brill, 2013), 148.

¹¹⁹ MS London British Library Add. 27556, fols. 101r-101v.

¹²⁰ MS Frankfurt Universitätsbibliothek hebr. Oct. 17, fol. 11r. The recycling of a single tune for multiple songs reflects the medieval ideal that music should build on the familiar and not seek to differentiate itself from its predecessors. See Margot Fassler, *Music in the Medieval West* (New York: W. W. Norton and Company, 2014), 11.

¹²¹ On the continued centrality of the oral transmission of tunes in Jewish communities, Avery Gosfield, “I Sing it to an Italian Tune . . . Thoughts on Performing Sixteenth-Century Italian-Jewish Sung Poetry Today,” *European Journal of Jewish Studies* 8:1 (2014), 27-31; Idem., “Gratias post mensam,” 278-280 and 290-291.

Many of the melodies used for Shabbat Zemirot likely grew out of the urban musical environment in which both Jews and Christians participated.¹²² While some rabbinic figures prohibited their coreligionists from drawing musical inspiration from Christians, Jews continued to do so especially when singing paraliturgical songs like Shabbat Zemirot.¹²³ In a copy of *Maḥzor Vitry* dated to around 1204 in Northern France, a later hand added a marginal note instructing that the Shabbat Zemer *Dror Yikra* be sung to the tune of a French melody called “*Tuit cil qui vont en namoral*”.¹²⁴ This tune has been identified as the refrain *Tuit cil qui sont enamoraz* in the Old French poem *Court de Paradis* that describes a heavenly feast and celebration and for which a 13th-century manuscript provides notated music.¹²⁵

Figure 5 Musical notation for *Tuit cil qui sont enamoraz*, MS Paris Bibliothèque nationale Française 25532, fol. 334r.

Figure 6 Instruction to sing to the tune *Tuit cil qui vont en namoral*, MS New York Jewish Theological Seminary 8092, fol. 38v.

¹²² Colette Sirat, "Les manuscrits liturgiques des juifs en France médiévale", 338-9 ; Idelsohn, *Jewish Music*, 382-385. For a brief but helpful overview of Jewish liturgical tunes in a Christian context, see Shalev-Eyni, "The Aural-Visual Experience," 194-199.

¹²³ Discomfort with the use of Christian tunes is found across *Sefer Ḥasidim*, but particularly at p. 106 (#348). For an example from 16th-century Frankfurt, see below. For a general discussion on Jewish use of Christian tunes, see Diana Matut, "Die Sammlung im Kontext der Musizierkultur um 1600" in Idem., *Dichtung und Musik im frühneuzeitlichen Aschkenas* (Leiden: Brill, 2011), 39-61; Edwin Seroussi, "Jewish Music and Diaspora" in *The Cambridge Companion to Jewish Music*, ed. J. S. Walden (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 31-32.

¹²⁴ MS New York Jewish Theological Seminary 8092, fol. 39r.

¹²⁵ This poem and its music are edited in Eva Vilamo-Pentti, *La Court de Paradis* (Helsinki, 1953). On the identification of the tune, Anne Ibos-Augé, Brigitte Lesne, and Colette Sirat, "Du texte à la musique: enjeux d'une reconstruction mélodique" in *Philologie et Musicologie* (Paris: Classiques Garnier, 2019), 34 & 37-39. Raphael Loewe argues that Jews intentionally used certain Christian tunes due to a thematic link between the tune's original lyrics and its new Jewish liturgical home. Since *Tuit cil qui vont en namoral* describes a heavenly feast, one might see intentionality in its tune being used for a Shabbat Zemer. Raphael Loewe, "A 13th Century Piyyut Set to French Music" *Revue des études juives* 161 (2002), 83-96. On Jewish engagement with Old French literature, see Fudeman, *Vernacular Voices*, 120-121.

Centuries later, Yosef Yuspa Hahn (1570-1637) indicates that such borrowing was still common when he lambasts the community of Frankfurt for singing *Kol Mekadesh* to gentile tunes.¹²⁶

Hahn's complaints were clearly based in reality as Jews were frequently singing Hebrew and Yiddish songs to gentile tunes.¹²⁷ As integral members of medieval urban culture, Jews heard all kinds of music that they then took home with them to ornament their liturgical and daily life.¹²⁸

The simultaneous centrality of oral transmission and the existence of written records for the Shabbat Zemirot tradition accords with the understanding of the Jewish community as one dominated by what has been called "weak orality."¹²⁹ This is to say that, in medieval Jewish life, a combination of orality and literacy were used to transmit texts and rituals from one generation or community to the next.¹³⁰ Even though the numerous collections of Shabbat Zemirot constituted a written record, songs would have been primarily learned through singing. While it is true that Jews regularly sang their prayers and songs to specific melodies that were written down by Christians, Jews were unlikely to have been consulting those works. Eli Yassif has observed that such interplay between written and oral transmission tends to diversify a ritual's

¹²⁶ Hahn, *Yosef Ometz*, 177. For examples and discussion of the tunes of *Kol Mekadesh*, see Idelsohn, *Jewish Music in its Historical Development*, 384 and Naomi Cohn Zentner, *Reshuffling the Ashkenazic Musical Heritage in Domestic Spheres: The Singing of Zemirot Shabbat among Religious Zionists in Israel*, 56-67 [Hebrew].

¹²⁷ Diana Matut, "Die Sammlung im Kontext der Musizierkultur um 1600," 39-61. Avery Gosfield, "I Sing it to an Italian Tune," 9-52. The Jewish use of Christian tunes was entirely commonplace. One specific example related to Shabbat Zemirot is noted by Israel Zinberg when he mentions a Shabbat song by Solomon Zelman of Erfurt (14th century) that was sung to the tune of the German folk-song *Herzog Ernst*. Israel Zinberg, *A History of Jewish Literature* (Cleveland: Press of Case Western Reserve University, 1975), vol. 7, 37-39.

¹²⁸ The use of these tunes for Shabbat Zemirot also speaks to a tension between pious and secular singing. *Sefer Hasidim* warns about the impiety of alehouse singing. *Sefer Hasidim*, ed. Wistinetzki, 9 (#11). By mixing urban tunes and liturgical poetry though, Shabbat Zemirot demonstrate how medieval "sacred and secular genres co-habit comfortably, in a state of mutual influence and interdependence." Haines, *Medieval Song*, 119-120.

¹²⁹ Brian Stock, *Listening for the Text: On the Uses of the Past* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1996), especially 5-6.

¹³⁰ For a discussion of orality and textuality in medieval music, see Leo Treitler, *With Voice and Pen: Coming to Know Medieval Song and How It Was Made* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003), 39-67 & 230-251.

performance. Discussing the Passover *Seder*, he writes that “The blend of written and oral traditions in a literate society may explain the diverse, dynamic nature of the Passover Haggadah, which exists side-by-side with the unchanging literary framework in which the different materials are ‘encaged.’”¹³¹ The same can also be said about the practice of singing Shabbat Zemirot for which there was a core set of songs, but still extreme diversity in performances.

This variegation is displayed in nearly every feature of Shabbat Zemirot. At the most basic level, different manuscripts record slightly different versions of various songs. Across collections, stanzas might be ordered differently,¹³² and occasionally some are missing entirely.¹³³ Deviations and mistakes are an inherent part of the scribal culture, but these differences are likely the result of scribes copying down the local or familial oral tradition with which they were most familiar.¹³⁴ The influence of locality is best evidenced by the fact that it is exceedingly rare to find two identical sets of Shabbat Zemirot outside of the French and Italian collections that contain only a few songs. While there was general agreement on certain core components, every collection assembles its own repertoire in its own order, likely according to the local custom.¹³⁵ As a result, many collections include among the Shabbat Zemirot songs that do not appear in any other collection.¹³⁶ Alongside the broad Ashkenazic and Italian Shabbat

¹³¹ Eli Yassif, “Oral Traditions in a Literate Society: The Hebrew Literature of the Middle Ages” in *Medieval Oral Literature*, ed. K. Reichl (Berlin: de Gruyter, 2016), 504.

¹³² See, for example, how the concluding stanzas of *Mah Yedidut* are reversed in MS Modena Biblioteca Estense Universitaria a.U.7.10, fols. 3v-4r and MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina 2231, fols. 10r-11r.

¹³³ MS Austrian National Library Hebr. 5386, fol. 2v.

¹³⁴ On the interchange between the oral and the textual in the spread of liturgy, see Virginia Reinburg, “Oral Rites: Prayer and Talk in Early Modern France” in *Spoken Word and Social Practice*, eds. T. V. Cohen and L. K. Twomey (Leiden: Brill, 2015), 387-392.

¹³⁵ Locality influenced the formation of all medieval Jewish liturgical traditions as each city or region had their own custom. Elisabeth Hollender, “Reconstructing Manuscripts: The Liturgical Fragments from Trier” in *Genizat Germania: Hebrew and Aramaic Binding Fragments from Germany in Context*, ed. A. Lehnardt (Leiden: Brill, 2010), 66-67. Since Shabbat Zemirot performances were organized around the home rather than the synagogue, it is likely that their performances were even more diversified.

¹³⁶ For example, the songs *Ba-yom Shabbat E'a'seh Mishteh* and *Al Lakheini* appear as Shabbat Zemirot in only one manuscript. MS Giessen Universitätsbibliothek 742, fol. 10r-v. Other examples of unedited or even uncatalogued Shabbat Zemirot abound. In Appendix 2, manuscripts that contain such songs are marked with a plus (+).

Zemirot traditions whose spread was described above existed local or familial traditions that shaped how the custom was performed.

This same diversity was expressed in the divergent choreographies for singing Shabbat Zemirot. For example, there was no agreement regarding when one should sing. In Ashkenaz, instructions recorded in manuscripts containing Shabbat Zemirot suggest both during and after the meal as an appropriate time for singing.¹³⁷ In Italy, by way of comparison, singing is frequently assigned to the moments before the meal begins.¹³⁸ Some collections distinguish themselves further by linking songs with stages in the meal. One domestic prayer-book produced in 15th-century Ashkenaz separates *Menuḥa Ve-simḥa* from the other songs by placing it before Kiddush, suggesting that this song specifically was to be sung before the start of the meal.¹³⁹ Various marginal notes added by users and scribes indicate that in some households *Tzur Mishelo* was recited immediately before *Birkat Ha-mazon*.¹⁴⁰

While the written sources display clear heterogeneity, the actual performances of Shabbat Zemirot would have been even more varied as each family developed their own unique singing traditions.¹⁴¹ The practice of Israel Isserlein (1390-1460) demonstrates the power of household customs. We are told that he

would sing on Friday night *Kol Mekadesh*, *Mah Yedidut*, and sometimes *Mah Yafit* and sometimes another song relevant to the matter of the day such as *Maoz Tzur Yeshuati* on

¹³⁷ For opinions that instruct singing during the meal, see MS New York Jewish Theological Seminary 8092, fol. 38r; MS London British Library Add. 27200, fol. 89r; MS Paris Alliance Israélite Universelle 133H, fol. 133v; Yosef b. Moses, *Leket Yosher*, Vol. 1, 72. For after the meal, see MS London British Library Add. 27200, fol. 72r.

¹³⁸ MS Jerusalem National Library Heb. 8°1957, fol. 15v. This reflects an earlier French custom to sing chapters of the Psalms before the meal. See Aaron b. Jacob of Lunel, *Sefer Orhot Hayim*, 295.

¹³⁹ MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina 2231, fol. 6v.

¹⁴⁰ MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina 2231, fol. 8r; MS Paris Bibliothèque nationale hebr. 601, fol. 37r. See also, Avi Shmidman, "The Poems for the Grace after Meals," 11.

¹⁴¹ Reinburg similarly describes how Books of Hours were repositories of family prayers that were simultaneously passed down and reshaped by each generation. Reinburg, *French Books of Hours*, 53-83.

Ḥannukah. And during Shabbat lunch, *Barukh Hashem Yom Yom*, *Barukh El Elyon*, and *Yom Ze Mechubad* and sometimes another song relevant to the matter of the day.¹⁴²

While many popular songs are mentioned, Isserlein's routine left out staples of the Shabbat Zemirot tradition. As seen here, Shabbat Zemirot were sung not according to the instructions given on the page, but according to the whim of the singer. Only one of the three core daytime songs is mentioned as part of Isserlein's repertoire (*Barukh HaShem Yom Yom*). Instead of singing the songs as they appeared in manuscripts, Isserlein constructed his own personal repertoire that changed week to week depending on the Jewish calendar and on his personal preference. We have few witnesses to the familial customs of everyday Jews in the Middle Ages. In a 15th-century Italian manuscript containing Shabbat Zemirot, however, a marginal note observes that the Gallichi family would recite Psalm 61 in addition to the others already included.¹⁴³ While not exactly a Shabbat Zemer, this remark points to the role that local familial tradition likely played in shaping each family's domestic liturgy. In this way, the same flexibility that guided the recitation of Shabbat Zemirot in the home of Israel Isserlein also existed in Jewish homes throughout medieval Europe.

Shabbat Zemirot in the Age of Print

The medieval development and spread of Shabbat Zemirot described thus far ended when when the songs began to be printed in the 16th century. The first of these printings occurred in Prague in 1514 when 13 Shabbat Zemirot were brought to press as part of a domestic prayer-book, only the second Hebrew work to be printed in Ashkenaz.¹⁴⁴ Over the course of the 16th

¹⁴² Yosef b. Moses, *Leket Yosher*, vol. 1, 72.

¹⁴³ MS Jerusalem National Library Heb. 8° 1957, fol. 9v.

¹⁴⁴ *Seder zemirot u-birkat ha-mazon* (Prague, 1514). For background, Olga Sixtová, "Jewish Printers and Printing Presses in Prague 1512-1670 (1672)" in *Hebrew Printing in Bohemia and Moravia*, ed. Olga Sixtová (Prague: Jewish Museum, 2012), 33-35.

century, Shabbat Zemirot were printed in numerous other cities including Krakow (1539),¹⁴⁵ Mantua (1563), Lublin (1596),¹⁴⁶ and Basel (1599).¹⁴⁷ The songs in these collections roughly match those which appeared most frequently in 15th-century Ashkenazic collections.¹⁴⁸ At the same time, new collections containing Shabbat Zemirot composed by figures such as Solomon Luria (1510-1573) were being to be composed and printed as well.¹⁴⁹ The most popular new Shabbat table-songs were penned by Isaac Luria (1534-1572), Israel Najara (1555-1625), and other scholars residing in the city of Safed in Northern Palestine.¹⁵⁰ Many of their compositions became mainstays of Shabbat Zemirot repertoires after being printed during the 17th century. References to the medieval songs in these new collections indicate, though, that during the 16th century the pre-print Zemirot retained their cultural dominance.¹⁵¹

In the years immediately following the onset of print, contemporary observations indicate that singing Shabbat Zemirot was a staple Jewish practice.¹⁵² Menahem de Lonzano (1550-1626), an eastern Mediterranean itinerant scholar, writes that “there was a Jewish custom in the days of the ancestors to sing to the Blessed One on the eve of Shabbat and at the conclusion of

¹⁴⁵ In Krakow in 1539, 500 Zemirot books were published in two different sizes. Majer Balaban, “Zur Geschichte der Hebräischen Druckereien in Polen,” *Soncino-Blätter* 3:1 (July 1929), 43. On Krakow printings in 1580 and 1597, Marvin J. Heller, *The Sixteenth Century Hebrew Book* (Leiden: Brill, 2004), vol. 2, 647.

¹⁴⁶ The Zemirot of Solomon Luria were printed in Lublin in 1596. See: Heller, *The Sixteenth Century Hebrew Book*, vol. 2, 639.

¹⁴⁷ Heller, *The Sixteenth Century Hebrew Book*, vol. 2, 911.

¹⁴⁸ The earliest printing of the Italian repertoire identified by this author is *Siddur Mevarkha* (Venice, 1618).

¹⁴⁹ On Solomon Luria, see Yosaif M. Dubovick, “Zemirot Maharshal le-yom shabbat kodesh im peyrusho” in *Sefer Zikaron Ish Tevunah*, ed. E. Korach (Jerusalem: Ma’arekhet Ish Tevunah, 2014), 37-51; Idem., “Zemirot Maharshal le-leil shabbat kodesh im peyrusho,” *Yeshurun* 16 (2005): 845-859; Marvin J. Heller, *The Seventeenth Century Hebrew Book* (Leiden, 2011), vol. 1, 104-105.

¹⁵⁰ On Isaac Luria and the Zemirot penned in Safed, see Joseph Avivi, *Kabalat Ha-Ari* (Jerusalem: Mekhon Ben-Tsevi, 2008), vol. 1, 96; Yehuda Liebes, “Zemirot li-s’eudot shabbat,” 540-555; Lawrence Fine, *Physician of the Soul, Healer of the Cosmos* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2003), 150-258; Moshe Halamish, *Kabbalistic Customs of Shabbat*, 348-353; Tova Beerli and Edwin Seroussi, “Rabbi Israel Najara in Ashkenaz,” *Kabbalah* 33 (2015), 71-2.

¹⁵¹ Solomon Luria’s songs are assigned tunes from the medieval Shabbat Zemirot in *Birkat ha-mazon* (Venice, 1603).

¹⁵² On Christian mealtime singing, see Flora Dennis, “Scattered Knives and Dismembered Song: Cutlery, Music and the Rituals of Dining,” *Renaissance Studies* 24.1 (2010): 171-175.

Shabbat . . . and this custom is still prominent among the people of Ashkenaz, Italy, and other places.”¹⁵³ Though table singing goes unnamed here, his list of three Hebrew poets and other references to table-singing in his work make clear that Lonzano is referring to the popularity of singing Shabbat Zemirot.¹⁵⁴ The famed Christian Hebraist Johannes Buxtorf (1564-1629) similarly notes in his German ethnography of Jewish practice that “one can read in their *Benschen* or table-prayer-books, in which are written the table prayers for all holy and feast days throughout the year, rhymes in Hebrew and German. Among these is a prayer that starts *Mah jedidus menuchasech*,” which, as noted above, was a popular Shabbat Zemer.¹⁵⁵ While the manuscript sources demonstrate that Shabbat Zemirot were sung widely during the Middle Ages, these later Jewish and Christian observations along with frequent printings of the songs emphasize that table-singing had become a pervasive and visible Jewish practice by the 16th century.

Print also facilitated substantive development in the custom. Most notably, print standardized a pan-European repertoire of songs.¹⁵⁶ While the manuscript collections evidence a wide range of songs, editions printed across the continent during the 16th century are generally indistinguishable. The collections printed in Prague in 1514, in Mantua in 1563, in Krakow in 1580, and in Venice in 1600 contain the same Shabbat Zemirot in a nearly identical order. The regional diversity and varying popularity of songs that had defined medieval collections fades

¹⁵³ *Shete yadot* (Venice, 1618), 100r.

¹⁵⁴ Edwin Seroussi, “Rabbi Menaḥem de Lonzano – Ethnomusicologist” in *Meir Benayahu Memorial Volume*, eds. M. Bar-Asher, Y. Liebes, M. Assis and Y. Kaplan (Jerusalem: Carmel, 2019), vol. 1, 604 [in Hebrew].

¹⁵⁵ Johannes Buxtorf, *Juden-schul* (Basle, 1643), 340.

¹⁵⁶ Printing caused significant standardization of textual transmission and learning. See Elchanan Reiner, “The Ashkenazic Élite at the Beginning of the Modern Era: Manuscript versus Printed Book,” *Polin* 10 (1997): 85-98; Pavel Sládek, “The Printed Book in 15th- and 16th-Century Jewish Culture” in *Hebrew Printing in Bohemia and Moravia*, 9-30. For a liturgical example, see how print standardized the extremely variegated *Seliḥot* tradition. *Maḥzor l’Yamim Noraim*, ed. D. Goldschmidt (Jerusalem: Koren, 1970), 12-16.

away in the age of print. Along with a few post-medieval additions, the Shabbat Zemirot printed in the 16th century still dominate the collections in use today.¹⁵⁷

Innovation was also seen in the dissemination of new tools for engaging with the Zemirot. The most common of these were translations that were printed with some consistency during the 16th century and beyond.¹⁵⁸ While Yiddish translations dominated the presses, some late manuscripts with Italian translations demonstrate that there was a wide interest in making the songs accessible.¹⁵⁹ This movement towards understanding also engendered commentaries on the Zemirot. Piyyut commentary has a distinguished history in medieval Europe, but the Shabbat Zemirot never received serious attention from medieval commentators.¹⁶⁰ This began to change around the time of the first printing of the Shabbat Zemirot. Towards the end of the 15th century, an anonymous reader living in Italy wrote a self-described “commentary” on the Shabbat Zemirot in the marginalia of a manuscript copied earlier in the 15th century.¹⁶¹ Later, in 1580, the first extensive commentary on the Ashkenazi Shabbat Zemirot was published.¹⁶² The major goal of both the manuscript and published commentaries was, like the translations, to facilitate understanding. The 1580 commentary opens by remarking that “it is appropriate to explicate the songs in easy language so that they will be understood in the mouths of the masses.”¹⁶³ Both the

¹⁵⁷ For an interesting example of a Shabbat Zemer removed from the repertoire even after having been printed, see Nulman, “Mah Yafit,” 27-38.

¹⁵⁸ For a discussion of printing translations, see David Ruderman, *Early Modern Jewry: A New Cultural History* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2010), 105-110.

¹⁵⁹ On printed Yiddish translations, see Chava Turniansky, “The ‘Bentsherel’ and the Sabbath-hymns in Yiddish” *Alei Sefer* 10 (1982), 51-92 [in Hebrew]. For an Italian translation, MS London Montefiore Library 245, fols. 1r-7r.

¹⁶⁰ Elizabeth Hollender’s index lists no extant medieval commentaries on Shabbat Zemirot. Elizabeth Hollender, *Clavis Commentariorum of Hebrew Liturgical Poetry in Manuscript* (Leiden: Brill, 2005).

¹⁶¹ MS Parma Biblioteca Palatina 2231, fols. 8r-20v. See also 30v where the author describes his marginal comments as a “Peirush,” or commentary.

¹⁶² *Birkat ha-mazon* (Krakow, 1580). Later, the Shabbat Zemirot of Solomon Luria were printed with his commentary in 1603. Dubovick, “Zemirot Maharshal le-yom shabbat kodesh im peyrusho,” 37-51; Idem., “Zemirot Maharshal le-leil shabbat kodesh im peyrusho,” 845-859; Heller, *The Seventeenth Century Hebrew Book*, vol. 1, 104-105.

¹⁶³ *Birkat ha-mazon* (Krakow 1580), 12r.

works elucidate the dense poetic language, clarify rabbinic references, and draw out the pious lessons embedded in the lyrics.

This new interest in comprehension coupled with the emergence of a more rigidly defined repertoire highlights a broader shift in how Shabbat Zemirot were understood. While for most of the Middle Ages singing was a pious pastime that enlivened Shabbat, after being printed, the songs began to be conceived of as a more structured Shabbat ritual. Take, for example, Yosef Yuspa Hahn (1570-1637) of Frankfurt who notes that “all my students are careful to sing every Shabbat evening.”¹⁶⁴ This language of being careful (נוהרין) is reflective of the fulfillment of a religious obligation and highlights the seriousness, not found in earlier sources, with which he and his students related to Shabbat Zemirot.¹⁶⁵ Hahn played a role in constructing and spreading this new, more stern relationship with table-singing when he called on community leaders to take a stand against the use of Christian tunes and the participation of women in singing.¹⁶⁶ Later figures continued down this path of policing the performance of Shabbat Zemirot.¹⁶⁷ Most notably, the Polish rabbi Avraham Gombiner (1635-1682) sought to put an end to the singing of any table-songs that were not traditionally designated as Shabbat Zemirot.¹⁶⁸

The reification of Shabbat table-singing into a structured ritual began already at the end of the 12th century when northern French scribes first copied repertoires of songs into liturgical collections for recitation specifically at Shabbat meals. As the songs spread via oral transmission and manuscript copies during the Middle Ages, the custom maintained its flexibility as a Shabbat

¹⁶⁴ Hahn, *Yosef Ometz*, 175.

¹⁶⁵ For similarly serious approaches taken to the singing of Shabbat Zemirot in early modern mystical sources, see Moshe Halamish, *Kabbalistic Customs of Shabbat*, 344-5.

¹⁶⁶ Hahn, *Yosef Ometz*, 177.

¹⁶⁷ Nephtali Tokayer, “*Li-birur emdatam shel gedolei ha-poskim al minhag amirat ha-zemirot bi-seudot ha-shabbat*” *Shematin* 145 (2001), 66-75. For comparable Christian attempts to police singing, see Trocme-Latter, *The Singing of the Strasbourg Protestants*, 129-131.

¹⁶⁸ Tokayer, “*li-birur emdatam shel gedolei ha-poskim*,” 70-71.

pastime. Printing, though, ushered in a new era by standardizing a loosely bound collection of songs into a pan-European liturgical text worthy of study and demanding rigidity. This is not to say that Shabbat Zemirot ever ceased to be a joyous Shabbat pastime, but that the custom and its songs grew to occupy a different space for some early modern Jews.

Conclusion:

In a recent article about the medieval singing voice, the authors open by lamenting that “scholars and performers have access to medieval musical notation but we do not have access to medieval sounds; the perceptions are based on the singing voices of the living but informed by documents created by those long dead, whose sounds we have never heard.”¹⁶⁹ The same hard truth can be said about the domestic singing explored in this article. We do not know exactly which Shabbat Zemirot were sung in medieval Jewish homes or how; all we have is the expanding source material that was generated beginning at the end of the 12th century. Yet, as we have seen, even this evidence can allow us “to enter by various small doors into the huge realm resounding with the many voices of medieval authors, singers and scribes.”¹⁷⁰ The Shabbat Zemirot and their accompanying literature offer a rare peek into a form of everyday medieval domestic piety that cannot be neglected. The detailed development of this rich practice, which has been outlined here, is worthy of further scholarly analysis. Just like the liturgy of the synagogue, analysis of the Shabbat Zemirot themselves and their place within their specific manuscript contexts can illuminate important trends in localized Jewish ritual life and domestic

¹⁶⁹ Katrina Livljanic and Benjamin Bagby, “The Silence of Medieval Singers” in *The Cambridge History of Medieval Music*, 210.

¹⁷⁰ *Ibid.*, 210-211.

piety. Though the evidence consists of words on a page as opposed to voices resounding from the home, it still has much to tell us.

Appendix 1: Shabbat Zemirot Collections in Manuscript

This is a list of the manuscripts containing Shabbat Zemirot that were identified for this study. The determination of each manuscript's provenance is generally based upon the most authoritative catalogues, which have been cited with each manuscript.¹⁷¹ Any additional published material that was helpful for determining the provenance is added in the footnotes. I would like to thank Dr. Justine Isserles for her generous assistance dating those manuscripts that have yet to be thoroughly described in print. It should be noted that regional terminology reflects that used by Richler and Beit-Arie. Unlike within the body of this article, the identification of a manuscript's place of origin as Ashkenaz in the appendix indicates that it could have been produced in either Germany or France. If manuscripts have been digitized, links are provided to the landing page from which one is able to view the digitized version on the holding library's website or alternatively on Ktiv. The inclusion of an asterisk (*) indicates that at least one Shabbat Zemer in the collection appears to have been added by a later hand.

Ashkenazic Repertoire:

1. *Maḥzor Vitry*. Moscow, Russian State Library, MS Guensburg 481, northern France, after 1171, fol. 335r-v.¹⁷²
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990001465590205171

¹⁷¹ The cited catalogues ordered alphabetically according to editors are: *Catalogue of the Hebrew Manuscripts in the Bodleian Library: Supplement of Addenda and Corrigenda to Vol. 1*, ed. Malachi Beit-Arie (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1994); *Catalogue des manuscrits et livres rares hébraïques de la Bibliothèque du Talmud Tora de Livourne*, ed. Carlo Bernheimer (Livourne: Comune di Livorno, 1916); *Catalogo dei manoscritti Orientali della Biblioteca Estense*, ed. Carlo Bernheimer (Rome: Istituto Poligrafico dello Stato, 1960); *Catalogue of the Hebrew and Samaritan manuscripts in the British Museum*, ed. G. Margoliouth, 4 vols. (London: British Museum, 1899-1935); *Catalogus librorum manuscriptorum qui in Bibliotheca senatoria civitatis lipsiensis asservantur*, ed. Robert Naumann (Grimae: J. M. Gebhardt, 1838); *Catalogue of the Hebrew manuscripts in the Bodleian Library and in the college libraries of Oxford*, ed. Adolf Neubauer, 2 vols. (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1886-1906); *Hebrew manuscripts at Cambridge University Library: A Description and Introduction*, ed. Stefan Reif (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997); *Hebrew manuscripts in the Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana: Catalogue*, ed. Benjamin Richler (Città del Vaticano: Biblioteca apostolica vaticana, 2008); *Catalogue of the Hebrew manuscripts in the Biblioteca Palatina Parma*, ed. Benjamin Richler (Jerusalem: Jewish National and University Library, 1997); Cecil Roth, "Catalogue of the Manuscripts in the Roth Collection" in *Alexander Marx Jubilee Volume: English Section* (New York: Jewish Theological Seminary, 1950), 503-535; *Handschriften der Stadt- und Universitätsbibliothek Frankfurt am Main: Hebraische Handschriften*, eds. Ernst Roth & Leo Prijs, 3 vols. (Wiesbaden: Steiner, 1982-1993); Gustavo Sacerdote, "Catalogo dei Codici Ebraici della Biblioteca Casantense" in *Cataloghi dei codici orientali di alcune biblioteche d'Italia*, ed. (Firenze: Tipografia dei successori Le Monnier, 1897), 477-662; *Die hebräischen Handschriften der Nationalbibliothek in Wien*, ed. Arthur Schwarz (Leipzig: K.W. Hiersemann, 1925); *Die hebräischen Handschriften der K. Hof- und Staatsbibliothek in Muenchen*, ed. Moritz Steinschneider (Munich: Commission der Palm'schen Hofbuchhandlung, 1895); *Katalog der hebräischen Handschriften und Bücher in der Bibliothek des Professors Dr. David Kaufmann*, ed. Miksa Weisz (Frankfurt: J. Kauffmann, 1906).

¹⁷² Justine Isserles, "Maḥzor Vitry: A Study of Liturgical-Halakhic Compendia from Medieval Franco-Germany", *Jewish History* (2021) (forthcoming)

2. *Maḥzor Vitry*. New York, Jewish Theological Seminary MS 8092, northern France, c. 1204, fol. 38r-v.¹⁷³
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990001112520205171
3. *Maḥzor Vitry*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 2574, northern France, Late 12th – very early 13th century, fol. 74r*. De Rossi #159, Richler, *Palatina* #1053.¹⁷⁴
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990000838550205171
4. *Maḥzor Vitry*. Oxford, Bodleian Library, MS Opp. 59, northern France/Germany, late 12th-early 14th centuries, fols. 107v-113r [Shabbat Zemiroth from northern France in the late-12th or early-13th century]. Neubauer/Beit-Arie #1100.¹⁷⁵
5. *Maḥzor Vitry*. London, British Library Add. MS 27200, northern France, 1242, fols. 72r-v & 89r-90r. Margoliouth #655.¹⁷⁶
http://www.bl.uk/manuscripts/FullDisplay.aspx?ref=Add_MS_27200
6. *Maḥzor French Rite*. Città del Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, MS ebr. 322, northern France, Mid-late 13th century, fol. 69r*. Richler, *Vatican*, pp. 271-273.
<https://digi.vatlib.it/mss/detail/Vat.ebr.322>
7. *Miscellany*. London, British Library, Add. MS 11639, northern France, 1278, fols. 533r-534r. Margoliouth #1056.¹⁷⁷
http://www.bl.uk/manuscripts/FullDisplay.aspx?ref=Add_MS_11639
8. *Maḥzor Vitry*. Paris, Alliance Israélite Universelle, MS 133H, northern France, 1280-1300, fols. 133v-135v.¹⁷⁸
9. *Sabbath hymns and piyyutim for weddings and circumcisions*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 1931, Germany, 1300, fols. 14v-29v. De Rossi #352, Richler, *Palatina* #1095.¹⁷⁹

¹⁷³ E. D. Goldschmidt “The Reggio of Maḥzor Vitry” in *On Jewish Liturgy*, 66-67; Isserles, “Maḥzor Vitry.”

¹⁷⁴ Isserles, “Maḥzor Vitry.”

¹⁷⁵ This manuscript is made up of multiple sections composed by five scribes from both northern France and Germany. Justine Isserles argues that the sections containing Shabbat Zemiroth are part of the earliest section of this work which was composed in northern France in either the late 12th- or early 13th-century. Isserles, “Maḥzor Vitry.”

¹⁷⁶ Isserles, “Maḥzor Vitry.”

¹⁷⁷ For a detailed description, see Malachi Beit-Arié, “The Making of the Miscellany,” in ed. Jeremy Schonfield, *The North French Hebrew Miscellany (British Library Add. MS 11639): Companion Volume to an Illuminated Manuscript from the Thirteenth Century France in Facsimile* (London: Facsimile Editions, 2003), 47-73.

¹⁷⁸ Dated by Isserles, “Maḥzor Vitry.” Described by Sirat, “Un nouveau manuscrit du Maḥzor Vitry” *Revue des Études Juives* 75 (1966), 245-266.

¹⁷⁹ Beit-Arié describes this manuscript as coming from Ashkenaz generally. The links between this manuscript and the liturgical sections composed in German-speaking lands found in MS Oxford Bodleian Library Opp. 59 suggests

https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS990000833040205171

10. *Maḥzor*. Giessen, Universitätsbibliothek, MS 742 (fragments), Germany, late 13th – early 14th century, fol. 10r-v.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS990027028530205171

11. *Songs*. Leipzig, Universitätsbibliothek, MS B.H. duod. 43, Germany, 13th – 14th century, fols. 38r-38v & 43r-45v* [Shabbat Zemirot added in the 14th Century]. Naumann #XXV (p. 290).
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS990026278110205171

12. *Siddur According to the German Rite*. London, British Library, MS Add. 27556, Germany, 14th century, fols. 98r-101v. Margoliouth #653.
http://www.bl.uk/manuscripts/FullDisplay.aspx?ref=Add_MS_27556

13. *Songs*. Vienna, Österreichischen Nationalbibliothek, MS Cod. hebr. 5386 (fragments), Germany, 14th century, fols. 2v-3r.¹⁸⁰
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS990026385080205171

14. *Siddur Eastern Ashkenazic rite*. Città del Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, MS ebr. 323, Germany, Early 14th to 15th century, fols. 171v-173v. Richler, *Vatican*, pp. 273-275. <https://digi.vatlib.it/mss/detail/Vat.ebr.323>

15. *Shabbat Songs*. Munich, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, MS Heb. 339, Germany, 14th-15th century, fols. 14r-33v. Steinschneider, #339 (pp. 183-184). <https://daten.digital-sammlungen.de/~db/0011/bsb00117578/images/>

16. *Prayers recited at the dining table*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 1912, Germany, 15th century, fols. 21v-42r. De Rossi #697, Richler, *Palatina* #1104.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS990000936840205171#

17. *Zemirot*. Modena, Biblioteca Estense Universitaria, MS a.U.7.10, Italy, 14th – 15th century, fols. 1r-10v. Bernheimer, *Estence* #28.¹⁸¹

a shared origin in Ashkenaz. Beyond the two manuscripts containing very similar Shabbat Zemirot, Gabriel Wasserman has helpfully pointed out that these two manuscripts contain very similar unique readings of the wedding song *Shaddai Maggid*.

¹⁸⁰ The pencil ruling in this fragment indicates that it was produced in the 14th century.

¹⁸¹ This manuscript was copied in a clear Italian book-hand, yet—as noted by Bernheimer—it contains the liturgical custom of German-speaking lands. I have included it with the Ashkenazic collections because the Shabbat Zemirot

https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS990001777300205171

18. *Prayers for various occasions*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 2231, Ashkenaz, 15th century, fols. 6v-20r [marginal notes added in Italy]. De Rossi #852, Richler, *Palatina* #1105.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS990001777300205171
19. *Mealtime Prayers*. Città del Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, MS ebr. 328, Germany, Late 15th century, fols. 12r-26v. Richler, *Vatican*, p. 281.
<https://digi.vatlib.it/mss/detail/Vat.ebr.328>
20. *Miscellany*. Munich, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, MS Heb. 401, Ashkenaz, 1506-1519, fols. 191r-193v. Steinschneider, #401 (pp. 220-224). <https://daten.digital-sammlungen.de/~db/0010/bsb00103868/images/>

Italian Repertoire:

1. *Commentary on Minor Prophets*. Oxford, Bodleian Library, MS Canonici, Or. 33, Treviglio(?), northern Italy, 1358, fol. 125r/v* [Shabbat Zemirot added no later than the 15th Century]. Neubauer/Beit-Arie #317.
https://hebrew.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/catalog/manuscript_246
2. *Collectaneous Volume*. Cambridge, University Library, MS Add. 2580, northern Italy, 1396, fol. 2r*. Reif, pp. 172-173.¹⁸²
3. *Maḥzor – Roman Rite*. London, British Library, MS Add. 26998, Cento, northern Italy, 1397, fol. 148r/v. Margoliouth #628.¹⁸³
http://www.bl.uk/manuscripts/FullDisplay.aspx?ref=Add_MS_26998
4. *Liturgy for the Whole Year - Roman Rite*. Leeds, University Library, Cecil Roth Collection, MS 9, Italy, 14th-15th century, fols. 158v-160r*. Roth, #9.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS990001855900205171

found here clearly derive from that tradition. The later addition of a Zemer written by the Ashkenazic rabbi, Israel Isserlein, for the conclusion of Shabbat further suggests that the manuscript was used by those operating within an Ashkenazic cultural orbit.

¹⁸² Though composed in an Ashkenazic script, this manuscript is identified in Sfordata as coming from Italy. The Shabbat Zemirot that were added to its opening folios support this contention.

¹⁸³ Margoliouth misdates this manuscript to 1298 based upon the colophon. This has been noted as a mistake and corrected in the Sfordata catalogue based upon an identification of the scribe.

5. *Maḥzor – Roman Rite*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 3132, Macerata, central Italy, 1403, fols. 36v-37r. De Rossi #61, Richler, *Palatina* #924.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990001133410205171#

6. *Siddur for the Whole Year – French Rite*. Budapest, Library of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Kaufmann Collection, MS A 370, northern Italy, c. 1418-1422, pp. 757-758. Weisz, #A370 (pp. 117-119).¹⁸⁴
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990026836920205171

7. *Siddur – Roman Rite*. Rome, Biblioteca Casanatense, MS 1965, Italy, 15th century, fols. 10v-13v and 35r-39r. Sacerdote #80 (p. 539).
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990001726650205171

8. *Prayers*. Paris, Bibliothèque nationale, MS hébreu 601, Italy, 15th century, fols. 34v-38v.
<https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b105406658>

9. *Maḥzor for the Whole Year – Roman Rite*. Private Collection (NLI Film Number: MSS-D 1686), 59r-61v. Italy, 15th century.

10. *Prayer-Book According to the Roman Rite*. Cambridge, University Library, MS Add. 491.1, Italy, 15th century, fols. 9v-10r. Reif, p. 233.

11. *Psalms*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 1721, Italy, 15th century, fols. 2r-3r and 84v-85r. De Rossi #865, Richler #401.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990000841710205171

12. *Prayers and Songs*. Jerusalem, National Library of Israel, MS Heb. 8°1957, Italy, 15th century, fols. 16v-19r. Bernheimer, *Talmud Tora*, #99.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990000415060205171

13. *Siddur – Roman Rite*. Città del Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, MS ebr. 594, central or northern Italy, mid-15th century, fols. 69v-73v. Richler, *Vatican*, p. 491.
<https://digi.vatlib.it/mss/detail/Vat.ebr.594>

14. *Collection of Various Works*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 2306, Italy, 15th – 16th century, fol. 11v [Zemiroth section from mid-15th Century]. De Rossi #1050,

¹⁸⁴ The manuscript was written in a northern French hand but was most likely copied in northern Italy by recently expelled French immigrants. For dating information, see Sacha Stern, “Christian Calendars in Hebrew Medieval Manuscripts,” *Medieval Encounters* 22 (2016), 247-248.

Richler, *Palatina* #1420.

https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990000793490205171

15. *Siddur – Roman Rite*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 2069, Italy, 1453, fols. 337r-338v* [Shabbat Zemiroth added in the 15th century]. De Rossi #383, Richler #928.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990000834070205171
16. *Common Prayers*. Oxford, Bodleian Library, MS Canonici Or. 18, northern Italy, mid to late-15th century, fols. 33v-37v. Neubauer/Beit-Arieh, #1062.
https://hebrew.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/catalog/manuscript_229
17. *Siddur – Roman Rite*. Città del Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, MS Ross. 357, Reggio d'Emilia, northern Italy, 1473, fols. 106v-107v. Richler, *Vatican*, pp. 570-571.
https://digi.vatlib.it/view/MSS_Ross.357/0001
18. *Siddur – Roman Rite*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 2232, Italy, 1475, fols. 13r-18v. De Rossi #1326, Richler, *Palatina* #934.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990000830270205171
19. *Miscellany*. London, British Library, MS Add. 18693, Italy, 1478, fols. 42r-43v. Margoliouth #639. http://www.bl.uk/manuscripts/FullDisplay.aspx?ref=Add_MS_18693
20. *Maḥzor Compendium*. Oxford, Bodleian Library, MS Canonici Or. 27, Mantua (Italy), 1481, fols. 286v-289r. Neubauer/Beit-Arie #1071.
https://hebrew.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/catalog/manuscript_239
21. *Miscellaneous*. Città del Vaticano, Biblioteca Apostolica Vaticana, MS ebr. 410, Italy, late-15th century, fols. 3r-6v. Richler, *Vatican*, pp. 354-355.
<https://digi.vatlib.it/mss/detail/Vat.ebr.410>
22. *Prayers – Roman Rite*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 1922, northern Italy, late-15th century, fol. 1r-v. De Rossi #1116, Richler, *Palatina* #980.
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23. *Siddur – Roman Rite*. Vienna, Österreichischen Nationalbibliothek, MS Cod. hebr.87, northern Italy, 1492, fols. 116v-119r. Schwarz #95.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990001692650205171

24. *Prayers and Blessings*. Cincinnati, Hebrew Union College, MS 279, Italy, 15th – 16th century, fols. 13v-17v.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990001095610205171
25. *Siddur for Weekday and Shabbat – Roman Rite*. St. Petersburg, Russian State Library, Firkovitch Collection, MS EVR I 145, Italy, 15th-16th century, fols. 46r-49r.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990001513080205171
26. *Siddur – Roman Rite*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm., 1739, Italy, 1504, fols. 84v-88r. De Rossi #561, Richler, *Palatina* #1007.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990000860230205171
27. *Liturgy for the Whole Year - Italian Rite*. Leeds, University Library, Cecil Roth Collection, Italy, 1514, MS 9, fols. 24v-25v. Roth #3.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990001855820205171
28. *Melodies and Songs*. 3, Frankfurt, University Library, MS hebr. Oct. 17, northern Italy, 1516, fols. 1v-3r & 11r-v Roth/Prijs #17.¹⁸⁵ <http://sammlungen.ub.uni-frankfurt.de/mshebr/content/titleinfo/1828426>
29. *Book of Job*. Parma, Biblioteca Palatina, MS Cod. Parm. 2695, Italy, early-14th century, fols. 36v-37r* [Zemirot dated to 16th Century]. De Rossi #1391, Richler, *Palatina* #322.
https://web.nli.org.il/sites/NLIS/en/ManuScript/Pages/Item.aspx?ItemID=PNX_MANUSCRIPTS_990000821420205171
30. *Siddur for the Whole Year – Roman Rite*. London, British Library, Or. MS 13525, Italy, 16th century, fols. 44r-47v. http://www.bl.uk/manuscripts/FullDisplay.aspx?ref=Or_13525

Appendix 2: Shabbat Zemirot in Manuscript

The below tables catalogue the Shabbat Zemirot found in the above listed manuscripts. This, though, is not an exhaustive list. Songs which appear in only one of the above collections are excluded from the tables below. Those manuscripts which include additional songs not listed in the catalogue are marked with a plus (+). Reference to each song's appearance in Israel Davidson's *Thesaurus of Medieval Hebrew Poetry*, 4 vols. (New York: KTAV, 1970) is provided. Songs that were added by a later hand are marked with an asterisk (*). Songs which appear only partially in the manuscript are marked with a caret (^).

¹⁸⁵ This manuscript contains some songs associated more strongly with the Ashkenazic rather than the Italian tradition.